

raisd

Reshaping Attention and Inclusion Strategies for Distinctively vulnerable people among the forcibly displaced

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Working Methodology and Guidelines

Deliverable D3.2

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About RAISD	
Call (part) identifier	H2020-SC6-MIGRATION-2018
Topic	MIGRATION-08-2018 Addressing the challenge of forced displacement
Fixed EC Keywords	Globalisation, migration, interethnic relations
<p><i>Forced displacement crises overcome societies and institutions all over the world. Pushed by the urgencies rather than events, solutions are frequently reactive, partial, and disregard some groups. The project 'Reshaping Attention and Inclusion Strategies for Distinctively vulnerable people among the forcibly displaced' (RAISD) aims at identifying highly Vulnerable Groups (VG) among these forcibly displaced people, analysing their specific needs, and finding suitable practices to address them. The concept of 'vulnerability context' considers the interplay between the features of these persons and their hosting communities, their interactions and experiences, and how different solutions for attention and inclusion affect them. As a result of this work, a methodology to carry out these studies will be developed. These goals are aligned with the call. They pursue characterizing these migrations and developing suitable aid strategies for them. The Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) frames the project. It proposes that all actors (including civil society) co-design actions, transversely integrates the gender perspective, and supports sustainability. Our research strategy will be based on methodological triangulation (i.e. the combined application of several methodologies). We will implement it through a specific participatory action research approach to fulfil the aim of undertaking advocacy-focused research, grounded in human rights and socio-ecological models. The team will work as a network of units in countries along migration routes. The units will promote the VG people' involvement, so they can speak with their own voices, gather information, and test practices. Work will rely on a tight integration of Social and Computer Sciences research. Automated learning and data mining will help to provide evidence-based recommendations, reducing a priori biases. A software tool will support collaboration, continuing previous H2020- funded RRI work.</i></p>	

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RAISD Glossary

AB	Advisory Board
ARU	Action Research Unit
ARUL	ARU Leader
CA	Consortium Agreement
CoU	Community of Users
CRIOS	Collaborative Research and Innovation Online Software tool
DMP	Data Management Plan
DPO	Data Protection Officer
EB	Executive Board
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
FD	Forced Displacement
FDP	Forcibly Displaced People / Person
GA	Grant Agreement
GUNI	Global University - Network of Innovation
HEIW	Higher Education in the World
IP	Intellectual Property
IPR	IP Rule
IS	Information Service
JCR	Journal Citation Reports
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LERU	League of European Research Universities
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
OpenAIRE	Open Access Infrastructure for Research in Europe
QAP	Quality Assurance Plan
R&I	Research and Innovation
REPAC	Research Ethics Policy and Advisory Committee
RRI	Responsible Research and Innovation
SC	Steering Committee
SDG	UN's Sustainable Development Goal
SO	Specific Objective
TAIS	Tailored Attention and Inclusion Strategy
UN	United Nations
UNHCR	UN High Commissioner for Refugees
UNRWA	United Nations Relief and Works Agency for Palestine Refugees in the Near East
VC	Vulnerability Context
VG	Vulnerable Group
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

The RAISD project Consortium 'Reshaping Attention and Inclusion Strategies for Distinctively vulnerable people among the forcibly displaced' hereby shares its *Work methodology & Guidelines* (Deliverable D3.2).

Lead and contributing partners of Task 3.1 [Development of the methodological framework]:

No	Name	Country	Role
1	Universidad Complutense De Madrid	Spain	Support partner and implementer
2	CESIE	Italy	Validation review, Rome meeting
3	UNIMED	Italy	Validation review, Rome meeting
5	Menedek-Migransokat Segito Egyesulet	Hungary	Validation review, Rome meeting

The present *Work methodology & Guidelines*, version 0.2, is part of WP3, Deliverable 3.2. *Work methodology & Guidelines on behalf of WPL UCM, Spain [January 2020]*. This document is a core component of Work Package (WP) 3 *Methodological coordination*.

Its aim is to offer the compilation of tools, methodological debates and exchange produced among partners from July to December 2019. It favours the exchange of the expertise and knowledge among the partners. Besides it provides practical procedures to help RAISD partners' work for the methodological design and execution of the next steps of the project. Thus, it ensures that the project tasks are aligned with the common scientific objectives, bringing consistency to the analytical and evaluation work, and practical arrangements in the other tasks and WPs.

This document is to be updated during the lifecycle of the project if needed, introducing further information as Milestone actions get finalised and reported.

D3.2. will receive input from the other scientific WPs: from WP4 *Vulnerability profiling* about the identification of profiles in VGs of FDP and their host communities; from WP5 *Design of TAIS* regarding attention and inclusion practices; from WP7 *Cross analysis* about the experiences in ARUs (WP6 *Action-research development*), the meetings with stakeholders, and the workshops.

In its late version, it will integrate the findings from all the WPs, particularly from WP4, WP5 and WP7. Its output will be the final methodology for the development of TAISs and the recommendations to actors for effective TAISs.

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose

The present document *Work methodology & Guidelines* is for the Horizon 2020 project “Reshaping Attention and Inclusion Strategies for Distinctively vulnerable people among the forcibly displaced (RAISD)”.

The main objective of the project is the identification of highly Vulnerable Groups VGs among Forcibly Displaced People FDP, and their specific challenges and needs, to be able to discover and provide Tailored Attention and Inclusion Strategies TAISs.

As such, it describes the procedures involved in the social research developed to identify the highly Vulnerable Groups (VGs) among the forcibly displaced people (FDP), their specific challenges and needs as well as the attention and inclusion practices available for them. The work methodology in RAISD is structured through the notion of ‘vulnerability context’.

The Vulnerability Context (VC) considers the specific features of the FDP group, hosting community, and institutions involved in a given setting, as well as their mutual interactions. The working hypothesis of the project was that effective and appropriate strategies of attention and inclusion to VGs of FDP need to be tailored to their specific VC. Thus, needs are related to contexts as well as to vital and migratory trajectories of individuals (Vulnerability profiling). The search of suitable practices to address specific VGs’ needs depend on the definition and identification of such Vulnerability Contexts (VCs) in each migration setting. Moreover, future satisfactory inclusion strategies will depend on the identification and characterization of current attention practices, because they are a key component of the VC.

According to the project main strategy, all research works have adopted a methodological triangulation approach. This triangulation refers to the application of several methodologies: Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI), action research, and socio-ecological models. Regarding the first two dimensions, it proposes potential possibilities for the analysis of patterns for interaction with stakeholders, and the rewarding or revalorisation strategies for stakeholders involved in the project (through an Action Research Unit (ARU) or outside it).

The document describes the techniques employed to gather information on refugees, host communities and organisations, as well as practices. It also refers to the procedures applied in the *Ethics Plan* in refugees’ research (D.3.1.). Besides, it collects evaluation techniques aligned with the common scientific objectives to process the collected data after fieldwork in order to contribute to D4.1. and D5.1.

It includes UCM work on methodological coordination from July to December 2019, and the result of several meetings online and offline with the partners. Such meetings are the Beirut Meeting of the project (converted to online meetings on October 21st, 22nd and 31st, 2019) and the Rome Meeting (December 9th-10th, 2019)¹. This work is related to project management issues concerning methodological issues, terminology clarification

¹ First to be held on 21st to 22nd October 2019 at Lebanese International University, Beirut. Due to the street manifestations and riots in Lebanon during the planned meeting days, the in- presence meeting was cancelled for participants’ safety. Online meetings to cover the key issues of the meeting was programmed for both days. An additional meeting in Rome was required by the consortium and established for 9-10th December 2019 in order to further discuss and get deeper insights for the issues in the initial consortium meeting agenda. The online meetings took place as follows: Monday, 21st October from 13:30 to 17:45, Tuesday, 22nd October from 9:30 to 17:30 and Thursday 31st October from 14:00 to 16:30.

and guidelines related to analysis of the data. Information obtained lead the project to the next step: to be able to discover and provide Tailored Attention and Inclusion Strategies (TAISs). Thus, the present document is to be used as a compilation discussion document for participants, as regards research procedures and analytical works, successive tasks, and next steps for related deliverables and connected Work Packages.

1.2 Application and validity

The procedures contained in this document are to be applied by all RAISD partners.

Revisions of the contents become valid from the date of issue.

1.3 Administration

The Coordination Office team (CO) of the project (i.e. Universidad Complutense de Madrid, UCM, partner number 1) is responsible for the elaboration of the document. Proposals for modifications or additions must be submitted to the CO, which updates and issues the revisions. All revisions need an approval by the Coordinator. Each new issue will be indicated in the revised document by means of a revision number.

1.4 Dissemination

The Work methodology & Guidelines and its annexes will be public at its latest version. First versions are confidential information available only for the beneficiaries and ARUs' members. It may be publicly circulated only with the approval of the Coordinator.

Copies of this document are distributed to each participant of the project at the issue date. It will also be available on the project Internal Collaborative Workspace (ICW).

2 Departure Point: Goals to achieve

2.1 Objectives, results and deliverables

RAISD aims to generate information, scientific knowledge, to solve specific problems, to succeed in practical applications for Vulnerable Groups among Forcibly Displaced People and hosting communities.

In order to do so, the project adopts a research strategy based on methodological triangulation: Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI), action research, and socio-ecological models; while gender perspective is applied mainstreaming.

Our research focus on vulnerability profiling and contexts (SO1, SO2, SO3, SO4) and testing (pilot experiment or TAIS) with social intervention projects (SO5, SO6, SO8). We are developing a Collaborative Research and Innovation Online Software tool (CRIOS) (SO7). Objectives are explained in figure 1 next page.

Figure 2 Objectives, Expected Results and Deliverables

2.2 Conceptual framework

2.2.1 RAISD key conceptualisation

One of the challenges of RAISD is that **concepts might be temporary tools** for the project as far as elaborating an updated conceptual framework is indeed one of the main objectives of the project.

On the other hand, **forced migration** is a subject where concepts and terminology is specially blurred. According to the International Organisation of Migration (IOM), the term forced migration is controversial because it alludes to the agency of human beings (the capacity of taking decisions) and because it highlights the narrowed interpretations that permit international protection to those forcibly displaced:

Forced Migration: A migratory movement which, although the drivers can be diverse, involves force, compulsion, or coercion. Note: While not an international legal concept, this term has been used to describe the movements of refugees, displaced persons (including those displaced by disasters or development projects), and, in some instances, victims of trafficking. At the international level the use of this term is debated because of the widespread recognition that a continuum of agency exists rather than a voluntary/forced dichotomy and that it might undermine the existing legal international protection regime. (IOM Glossary on Migration, 2019, 75).

Thus, we will find “refugees”, people in “refugee-like situation” and “asylum seekers”.

The first ones, “**refugees**”, face situations recognized under the 1951 Convention relating to the Status of Refugees and its 1967 Protocol, the 1969 OAU Convention Governing the Specific Aspects of Refugee Problems in Africa; those recognized in accordance with the UNHCR Statute; individuals granted complementary forms of protection; or, those enjoying “temporary protection” (UNHCR, 2013).

People in a **refugee-like situation**, include “groups of persons who are outside their country or territory of origin and who face protection risks similar to those of refugees, but for whom refugee status has, for practical or other reasons, not been ascertained” (UNHCR, 2013).

Asylum-seekers are persons who have applied for asylum or refugee status, but who have not yet received a final decision on their application (UNHCR, 2013).

IOM considers that a “**vulnerable group**” depends on the context. RAISD stresses research based on each territory in order to establish what groups are highly vulnerable among those forcibly displaced people.

Vulnerable Group: Depending on the context, any group or sector of society (such as children, the elderly, persons with disabilities, ethnic or religious minorities, migrants, particularly those who are in an irregular situation, or persons of diverse sex, sexual orientation and gender identity -SSOGI) that is at higher risk of being subjected to discriminatory practices, violence, social disadvantage, or economic hardship than other groups within the State. These groups are also at higher risk in periods of conflict, crisis or disasters (IOM Glossary on Migration, 2019, 226).

On the other hand, we should consider that -throughout the asylum application process- there are specific vulnerable people. Thus, a “**Vulnerable person**” (as defined by Directive 2013/32/EC, *Recast Asylum Procedures Directive*) is

related to: minors, unaccompanied minors, disabled people, elderly people, pregnant women, single parents with minor children, victims of trafficking in human beings, persons with serious illnesses, persons with mental disorders and persons who have been subjected to torture, rape or other serious forms of psychological, physical or sexual violence, such as victims of female genital mutilation.

Thus, OIM (2019, 226) understands “**Vulnerability**” as “the limited capacity to avoid, resist, cope with, or recover from harm. This limited capacity is the result of the unique interaction of individual, household, community, and structural characteristics and conditions.”

As a concept, vulnerability implies exposure to and susceptibility to some form of harm. There are different forms of harm, meaning that different sectors use the term differently (e.g. vulnerability to food insecurity, vulnerability to hazards, vulnerability to harm and violence and abuse, vulnerability to rights violation).

Vulnerability derives from a range of intersecting and co-existing personal, social, situational, and structural factors. For example, in crisis or disaster affected communities, individuals and groups may have different levels of vulnerability, depending on their exposure to hazards or to risks of neglect, discrimination, abuse and exploitation. The level of exposure is determined by the interplay of many factors: their sociodemographic characteristics, their capacities (including knowledge, networks, access to resources, access to information and early warnings, etc.), their location (in a camp, in a spontaneous settlement, in a transit centre, at the border, etc.) and the crisis induced factors having an impact on them (such as separation, loss and lack of resources and opportunities, discrimination in access to assistance, etc.) (IOM Glossary on Migration, 2019, 225-226).

Therefore, in RAISD we consider that effective strategies of attention and inclusion to those vulnerable groups need to be tailored to their specific **Vulnerability Context (VC)**.

With this regard, we consider that contexts that lack integration policies, social inclusive practices and human rights' assurance cause vulnerability among people (particularly if they already have specific needs).

Thus, finding a common concept of Vulnerability Context is an objective of the project.

By the term "**context**" we can understand the physical (with its territorial and geographical), political, institutional, cultural and historical space, in which a Vulnerable Group is located.

The interactions between the VGs and the local community, and with other actors, and stakeholders are part of this context.

RAISD considers that the refugee situation depends not only on the features of her/his Vulnerable Group, but also on the characteristics of the hosting community, and their mutual interactions.

At the same time, different types of care and inclusion practices are also part of the context. Informal and formal practices towards Forcibly Displaced People.

Therefore, context characteristics, including interactions and practices, would define the key components of a "vulnerability context". In this sense, "**Vulnerability**" is generated mainly by the context, because there is an absence of support processes for resilience generation².

We understand **resilience** as the ability of all human beings to cope and recover from stress. Stress could be caused by personal or environmental change or social, economic or political circumstances.

Asylum, Migration and Integration Fund Glossary

It is an on-line tool of AMIF. Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/home-affairs/e-library/glossary/asylum-migration-and-integration-fund_en

Eurostat Glossary

Dublin Statistics: https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php/Glossary:Dublin_statistics

Related concepts: [Application for international protection](#), [Asylum](#), [Asylum applicant](#), [Asylum decision](#), [Asylum recognition rate](#), [Repeated applicant](#) And other related to migration in "Population glossary": https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Category:Population_glossary

IOM- Toolkit on International Migration

Population Division Migration Section (2012). NY: UNDESA.

As stated in IOM's main page, it "provides an overview of basic definitions, concepts and sources for statistics on international migration, a summary of key messages, a quick guide to migration data and suggestions for further reading. This document was published by United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs (UN DESA), Population Division, Migration Section and developed under the Development Account Project on "Strengthening national capacities to deal with international migration: Maximizing development benefits and minimizing negative impact". Available at:

http://www.un.org/en/development/desa/population/migration/publications/others/docs/toolkit_DESA_June%202012.pdf

IOM- Glossary on Migration, 2019

Key terms that are used in the context of forced migration or forced/involuntary displacement include: forced migration, refugee, persons in a refugee-like, internally displaced persons (IDPs), mixed movement, disaster-induced migration, resettlement. There are two key glossaries:

2019. International Migration Law: Glossary on Migration. Available at

https://publications.iom.int/system/files/pdf/iml_34_glossary.pdf and most of them available as well at <https://www.iom.int/key-migration-terms>

² Definition of "Resilience", see Olsson, L., Jerneck, A., Thoren, H., Persson, J., & O'Byrne, D. (2015). Why resilience is unappealing to social science: Theoretical and empirical investigations of the scientific use of resilience. *Science Advances* 1(4), e1400217. doi: 10.1126/sciadv.1400217. Available at: <https://advances.sciencemag.org/content/1/4/e1400217>

No date. Key terms on Forced Migration. Definitions. Available at <https://migrationdataportal.org/themes/forced-migration-or-displacement>

The European Migrant Network (EMN) Glossary

Its aim is to improve “comparability by enabling a common understanding and use of terms and definitions relating to asylum and migration. The Glossary draws on a variety of sources, but primarily on the legislation of the EU asylum and immigration acquis, and makes terms available in the majority of EU Member State languages.” The actual version of the Glossary is version 6.0 and was updated in March 2018. https://ec.europa.eu/home-affairs/what-we-do/networks/european_migration_network/glossary_en

TRACKS-project (2016-2018) (HOME/2014/AMIF/AG/ASYL/7849) Glossary

The glossary is a part of the report “Identification and response to the needs of Trafficked Asylum Seekers. A Comparative Report For The Republic Of Cyprus, France, Ireland, Italy, Spain, The UK and Switzerland”, available at: <https://www.cear.es/wp-content/uploads/2018/03/TRACKS-consolidated-Report-January-2018.pdf>

UNHCR Statistical Online Population Database

UNHCR (2013) Statistical Online Population Database: Sources, Methods and Data Considerations. Available at: <https://www.unhcr.org/afr/statistics/country/45c06c662/unhcr-statistical-online-population-database-sources-methods-data-considerations.html#refugees>

3 Analytical and Evaluation Works

3.1 Techniques to gather information on refugees, host communities and organisations, and practices.

3.1.1 Participation of Stakeholders, interaction and rewarding

Participation of Stakeholders are the key of RAISD approach regarding Responsible Research and Innovation RRI & Participatory Action Research. RRI implies active participation in all phases of the project

The project implements a participatory action research approach to study vulnerable groups and vulnerability contexts, meaning that diverse stakeholders will be included in the process and asked about integration and inclusion policies and practices of forcibly displaced persons, and about possible tailored action strategies. Therefore, research techniques focus on the involvement of key stakeholders according to the principle of *quintuple helix* used in RRI. In RAISD it has referred to the collaboration of:

- 1) Civil society: Citizens; CSO (Civil society organisations, NGOs that work with refugees, internally displaced people, and asylum seekers; social innovators); and FDP and highly vulnerable groups among them.
- 2) Policymakers (or public services): national government, local and regional administration, international organisations).
- 3) Business: Industry (such as entrepreneurs, chamber of commerce, private companies, work centres); and Media³.
- 4) Scientists (academics, and organisations with research units).
- 5) Educators (educational community: schools, universities, colleges, NGOs).

Stakeholders have been called for the project public presentation, specific interviews, and other type of feedback for the project. Besides, key actors have been invited to be a permanent component of the project becoming a member of an **Action Research Unit (ARU)**. Thus, the project is implementing the RRI and PAR through a network of **Action Research Units (ARUs)**. Nevertheless, experts and external stakeholders' interviews also take place throughout the project.

In order to prepare stakeholders' involvement, several works take place in RAISD:

- Identification of stakeholders, individual and groups presentation of the project,
- Identification and agreement with a non-profit organisation specialised in the VGs of FDP (sometimes a *Memorandum of Understanding -MOU- between ARU's members* or a *Letter of commitment* are needed⁴).
- Constitution of an ARU according to the *Guidelines for the establishing of an ARU*.⁵

As already explained, each Action Research Units (ARU) works as a multidisciplinary group with representatives from all types of stakeholders according to the *quintuple helix* model of RRI. Each ARU has:

³ In RAISD each partner has considered if it is pertinent or not. In certain contexts free media should be considered as civil society, while in others it is seen as a stable productive sector (media industry news).

⁴ Universidad Complutense de Madrid, Spain (latest version May 2019).

⁵ UNIMED, Italy (latest version August 2019).

- a) Contributed to the research design providing feedback on preliminary works:
 - Identification of potential VGs.
 - Comments and opinions to change and improve the in-depth interview script for VGs.
 - Validation of questionnaire and its customisation (with a non-profit organisation specialised in the VGs of FDP or within the ARU).
- b) Carried out empirical fieldwork:
 - Contributing with specific data, documents and other sources of information to gather information to identify the VCs they face and the attention and inclusion practices that are addressed for VGs.
 - Taking part in participatory workshops⁶ and/or focus groups⁷.
 - Locating VGs' participants to interview.
 - Locating practices of attention and inclusion that are provided by different actors.
- c) Evaluation and feedback, and further steps:
 - ARU and stakeholders' involvement include participatory assessment and contribution to the analysis of the preliminary results obtained through the fieldworks. In order to do so, (possible) strategies to follow are:
 - o Individual presentations of main results and discussion and contrast with experts or specific stakeholders.
 - o Presentation as part of one or several workshops and/or focus groups within each ARU, where results are presented and discussed.

ARUs' work it is not collected by sound files or literal transcripts. Although audio recording could be useful.

As Morgan points out “most of what can be said about qualitative analysis of textual data applies equally well to transcripts of audio recordings from focus groups. The most distinctive issue in the analysis of focus groups results from situations where a single participant may repeatedly mention a particular topic or theme within a group. From an analytic point of view, this repetition leads to what focus group researchers call the need for group-to-group validation —so that any result that is considered to be important should be a major element of the discussion in most of the groups. More generally, the analysis of focus groups should pay special attention to the topics that consistently generate high levels of interest from almost every participant in almost every group” (2008, 354).

Independently, all information production must be **quickly systematised** in a Field Diary and tools provided.

⁶ To see a definition and the characterization of the technique see: Coghlan, D., & Brydon-Miller, M. (Eds.) (2014). *Participatory Action Research (PAR)*. The SAGE Encyclopedia of Action Research. SAGE.

doi: <https://dx.doi.org/10.4135/9781446294406.n259>. Examples of activities, please consult: Chambers, R. (2002). *Participatory Workshops. A Sourcebook of 21 Sets of Ideas and Activities*. London: Routledge.

⁷ For a definition and tips to dynamization, please consult: Morgan, D. L. (2008). Focus Groups. In L. M. Given (Ed.). *The Sage Encyclopedia of Qualitative Research Methods*. Thousand Oaks, California: SAGE. To a deeper insight of the technique see: Krueger, R.A., & Casey, M.A. (2009). *Focus Groups: A Practical Guide for Applied Research offers an easy-to-ready overview of sound focus group practices*. (Fourth edition). SAGE. An alternative is Liamputtong, P. (2011). *Focus Group Methodology. Principle and Practice*. SAGE.

It summarises the content of workshops/focus groups or stakeholders' interviews. It includes the following information:

- Place, date and length.
- Researcher/s reference.
- Short profile of the person interviewed or workshop/focus group participants.
- Notes on the content of the activity (on the topics covered and the information relevant to the investigation).
- Notes on the development of the interview/workshop or focus groups, and comments.

3.1.2 Procedures to apply the Ethics plan in refugees' research

Ethics is a mainstreaming issue in RAISD project, from the very beginning partners fulfilled the self-assessment "Ethical self-evaluation of project European Commission, DG Research and Innovation. How to complete your ethics" (2014). Moreover, two deliverables were provided regarding Ethics on building up national teams for the project and conducting the fieldwork (D1.1 and D.1.2., UCM)

Thus, research questions have been discussed among partners in meetings (offline and online) and preliminary questionnaires were designed along with other methodological tools and research procedures. All these tasks are necessary to guarantee quality and safeguard ethical practices.

Field-researchers' recruitment (NGO or academic) and training have been carefully carried out. In this sense, ethical requirements preparation and accessibility issues have been fulfilled before fieldwork took place. In order to do so, both a "Manual for Researchers: Work methodology and guidelines for the project"⁸ and a "Manual for Researchers: Information related to Ethics and Gender Issues"⁹ have been designed and disseminated among RAISD partners. Moreover, a "Quality Assurance Plan"¹⁰ and a "Ethics Plan"¹¹ were prepared for the consortium.

Therefore, as already stated in the *Data Management Plan* (CESIE, March 2019, 18) "The ethical aspects of data collection and research on them have been carefully considered. They include the intersecting issues of confidentiality, trust, risks to researchers, and potential harm to participants, as well as the broader cross-cutting issues of gender, culture, and power relationships, among others [Jacobsen and Landau, 2003; Mackenzie et al., 2007].

The **Ethics Plan** (Deliverable D3.1, Menedek, October 2019) was designed to ensure this perspective "containing the procedures to be followed by all the project participants and ARUs that are included in the action-research platform. The objective of ethical guidelines is to ensure that all RAISD Consortium partners work in an ethically acceptable way with respect to involving participants in any of its actions in the project. This plan specifies how the Consortium will maintain security, privacy and confidentiality norms, as well as common values of autonomy, independence, beneficence, non-maleficence and justice will be respected."

⁸ Universidad Complutense de Madrid, Spain (latest version July 2019)

⁹ Universidad Complutense de Madrid, Spain (latest version July 2019)

¹⁰ Universidad Complutense de Madrid, Spain (Deliverable D2.2) (latest version November 2019)

¹¹ Menedek, Hungary (Deliverable D3.1) (latest version December 2019)

The main ethical issues in RAISD project are:

- Data collection and interviews.
- Informed consent.
- Anonymity of interviewed people.
- Compensation to participants.
- Gender perspective
- Multi-functional teams and multi-perspective analysis
- Regular participatory assessments with representatives of all target groups

3.1.3 Characterization of the main sources of information

Sources of data and information available for the project were diverse. Stakeholders, vulnerable groups of forcibly displaced people, and scientific literature as well as statistic. Regarding countries' related secondary data an approximate period of reference was established from 2014 up to June 2019. Although this Deliverable 3.2. was mainly based in sources analysed from January 2015 to December 2019.

It is worthy to note that data-use approach has been employed for the fulfilment of the specific objectives of the project -all along its development- up to 2022.

Figure 2: RAISD Main Sources of Information

Types of literature and secondary data collected are heterogeneous. Scientific publications, stakeholders' reports and publications as well as databases provide the information needed to characterise Vulnerable Groups' profiles and needs as well as information from the context.

3.1.3.1 Primary sources

On the one hand, data collection from the Action Research Units members and other stakeholders' involvement are *a must* for the project. They are the experts on the field.

On the other hand, they have mainly led us to the identification of the highly vulnerable people to interview.

The identification of potential distinctively highly vulnerable people among FDP depended on each country/territory of research.

These vulnerabilities have implied gender, age, capability, origin, race, ethnicity, religion, sexual orientation, and displacement trajectory. Concerning vulnerable groups, interviews with individuals have comprised 175 personal semi-structured qualitative interviews (approximately 25 in each country). The "saturation"¹² criterion was employed to decide the number of interviews, focus groups and workshops.

Questions were predetermined but open-ended, besides, each interview guide was adapted to each RAISD's partner context (See Annex 3 Guide Interviews).

The interviews were recorded in audio and transcribed in the original language, then anonymised and translated into English (see 3.2. Primary Data Treatment).

3.1.3.2 Primary Data treatment

Anonymisation, transcription and translation of interviews into English are part of the procedures of data treatment after its collection, what alludes to its transcription and translation.

We have followed Oliver, Serovich and Mason (2005)¹³ considerations regarding transcription. They point out that in social sciences we usually employ a "naturalized approach" (language represents the real world). Therefore, the transcript usually reflects a verbatim depiction of speech: pauses, interjections, silences, grammatical failures, etc. (e.g., *Uh huh, Mm, Yeah*, etc.). Nevertheless, we won't be examining it for patterns (it will not be a "Conversation analysis"). However, we will consider the analysis of analysis of sentiments (feelings) so, (voice inflection: fear, cry,

¹² see Fusch, P. I., & Ness, L. R. (2015). Are We There Yet? Data Saturation in Qualitative Research. *The Qualitative Report*, 20(9), 1408-1416. Retrieved from <http://nsuworks.nova.edu/tqr/vol20/iss9/3>. Available at:

https://scholarworks.waldenu.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?referer=http://scholar.google.es/&httpsredir=1&article=1049&context=sm_pubs

Saunders, B., Sim, J., Kingstone, T., Baker, S., Waterfield, J., Bartlam, B., & Jinks, C. (2017). Saturation in qualitative research: exploring its conceptualization and operationalization. *Quality & quantity*, 52(4), 1893–1907. doi:10.1007/s11135-017-0574-8 Available at: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC5993836/>

¹³ For further considerations please consult: Oliver, D. G., Serovich, J. M., & Mason, T. L. (2005). Constraints and Opportunities with Interview Transcription: Towards Reflection in Qualitative Research. *Social forces; a scientific medium of social study and interpretation*, 84(2), 1273–1289. doi:10.1353/sof.2006.0023 <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC1400594/>

laugh, exaltation, doubts, and silences) are needed. It must also include verbatim depiction of speech (e.g., *Uh huh*, *Mm*, *Yeah*, etc.; vocalizations...); because they help to understand the meaning.

Data treatment carefully follows the “Data Management Plan” *Deliverable D9.1* and all RAISD ethical considerations.

As formulated in the RAISD Proposal technical and organisational measures that implemented to safeguard the rights and freedoms of the data subjects/research participants are various.

The procedures the partners will implement for the collection, storage, protection, retention and destruction of data comply with national and EU legislation. More specifically, with all the requirements that are legally established by the Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation). According to this text, all the processing of personal data will be lawful as all research subjects will provide their given consent for the purposes established in this report and that will be detailed in each consent form.

As it is stated in Article 9(1) and Article 89(1), the “processing of personal data revealing racial or ethnic origin, political opinions, religious or philosophical beliefs, or trade union membership, and the processing of genetic data, biometric data for the purpose of uniquely identifying a natural person, data concerning health or data concerning a natural person’s sex life or sexual orientation” will only be done if it is essential “for archiving purposes in the public interest, scientific or historical research purposes or statistical research purposes or statistical purposes”. Moreover, each data subject will have the right to obtain the erasure of personal data as mentioned by the “right to be forgotten” in Article 17 and will have the right to object “at any time to processing of personal data” (Article 21).

An anonymization procedure will be applied to all interviews in all countries in compliance with Article 89(1): “measures may include pseudonymisation provided that those purposes can be fulfilled in that manner. Where those purposes can be fulfilled by further processing which does not permit or no longer permits the identification of data subjects, those purposes shall be fulfilled in that manner”.

Anonymization is a must procedure after fieldwork. All transcriptions were anonymised and afterwards translated into English.

The key for the anonymization is that the interviewed persons should not be able to be identified or traced.

We employed data masking (personal data elements are removed to create a dataset where personal identifiers are not present¹⁴), and the substitution of real names by pseudonyms (their own name and that of other people); the substitution of places and territories that can identify the person interviewed.

¹⁴ Name and surname of the interviewee or other people. Name or surname of people working with the interviewees or helping them. Name of the city or village where the interviewee was born or lived. Instead of the name of the place, we should mention if it is a rural or urban area, and, in case you have this information, if according to the population density it could be consider a small village, a village, a town, a city or a big city. Name of the city or village where the interviewee is living nowadays. Instead of the name of the place, we should mention, for example: refugee camp in the border of Lebanon, Eastern Spanish city... Specific information that, according to the researchers, can allow the identification of the person. Instead of being so specific, try to provide more general data.

Each interview was recorded and stored with a number which is the reference for the transcription

- 1st digit: year, month, date of the interview.
- 2nd digit: Partner's number.
- 3rd digit: Number assigned to each researcher/interpreter.
- 4th digit: Number of interview produced by this specific researcher/interpreter.
- 6th digit: Number assigned related to interviewees' sex (woman, man, other).

As already explained in the RAISD proposal in order to guarantee the efficiency of the chain of anonymization, a set of technical measures aimed at concealing, masking and disassociating the personal data of the participants have been taken. "These will include both the microdata or direct identification data, and indirect identification data, that is, cross-referenced data from the same or different sources, which could allow the re-identification of a specific person, despite the fact that their information has been anonymized. Among the first group of data are name, location and date, and acquaintances. The last group would include data such as significant dates (e.g. birthdate or date of hospital admission), professions, membership in minority social groups, and economic income. If there were identification variables that could not be anonymized, these data would be removed from the previous process. In the choice of these operations, it must also be guaranteed that the process will not entail a distortion of the real data."

3.1.3.3 Secondary sources

3.1.3.3.1 Types of sources analysed

Regarding the compilation of statistical and secondary data, main sources followed this initial classification:

1) Statistics

Statistics on national/international migration flows. Each partner focused on its territory. Thus, information collected refers to:

- a. Statistics collected from governmental institutions.
- b. Statistics collected from international organisations.
- c. Academic researches and surveys.
- d. Non-governmental organisations researches.

2) Regulations

Legal regulations from National Government legislations related to immigration and the law of asylum and subsidiary protection, and norms regarding protection of victims of human trafficking.

3) Public Policies of public administrations:

IOM's Migration Governance Framework (MiGOF) defines migration policy as the "law and policy affecting the movement of people" and includes policy on "travel and temporary mobility, immigration, emigration, nationality, labour markets, economic and social development, industry, commerce, social cohesion, social services, health, education, law enforcement, foreign policy, trade and humanitarian" issues (IOM, 2017) . According to RAISD classification we distinguish between regulations (as defined mainly as laws) and policies which standardize attention to migrants/refugees and stand the principles that should follow.

Policies allude to central, regional and local institutions. Thus, they include local standards and plans that are relevant in the studied context. In certain contexts, local plans have a key impact on VGs. A key issue identify is the lack of information regarding policies that target vulnerable groups.

- a. Globally: information on policies is available at different sources, from which highlights the IOM-Global Migration Data Portal. Specifically, the "Migration policies and governance" page¹⁵. See next section.
- b. Regional scope: See EU information and data at the next section.
- c. Nationwide. Policies depend on funding from migration authorities, equality programmes and social services institutions. Its aims tend to promote the integration of migrants, claimants and beneficiaries of International Protection in general.

4) Institutional evaluations, diagnostics or studies:

They refer to institutional researchers providing information on vulnerable groups' profiling or situation, as well as reports and evaluations of public policies (or its lack of implementation). It includes evaluations on public administrations, situation diagnostics, studies on compliance with objectives, institutional evaluations, etc. Sources could be institutional, international organisations', NGOs' or academic.

As said before there is a lack of in-depth information regarding vulnerable groups in national contexts.

5) Media and Journalistic publications:

High quality journalistic or informative articles or articles should be included to reflect the trajectory of public policies, of the situation one or more of the vulnerable groups (VGs) in a certain territory. It can also help to illustrate changes or current trends regarding migrations, or specific events of importance to better understand the contexts.

This source of information is highly dependent on each country circumstances. An example of an European perspective see: <http://thenewarrivals.eu/> Some papers of interest regarding the EU area, are:

Austin, Thomas (2019) Benefaction, processing, exclusion: documentary representations of refugees and migrants in Fortress Europe, *Studies in European Cinema*, 16:3, 250-265, DOI: 10.1080/17411548.2019.1603029

6) Academic research:

¹⁵ Available at: <https://migrationdataportal.org/themes/migration-policies-and-governance>

This source of information alludes to articles in scientific journals, books or book chapters published on migrations of vulnerable groups (VGs), management of migratory flows in the area, inclusion of migrants, etc.

Research about vulnerable groups shows a contradictory panorama. On the one hand, literature on vulnerable groups refers to world-wide situations, or general characterizations of a group with specific or special needs with disregard of the specific context of attention. For instance, the research alludes to “women” as a homogeneous group without considering an intersectional perspective differentiating ethnicity, racialization, country of origin, sexual orientation, class, religion, etc. On the other hand, case studies or specific researches on groups in specific contexts are based on too small samples or refers to situations where generalisation for other contexts seems difficult.

Finally, Doctoral theses (PhD. Dissertations) related to any dimensions related to RAISD can be identified by sites such as <https://www.proquest.com> or <https://www.oclc.org/en/worldcat.html>

3.1.3.3.2 *References of Scientific Journals and literature are placed in Annex 1*

3.1.4 Databases and information for forthcoming tasks and international comparative

3.1.4.1 Availability, strength and limitations

Data sources from an international perspective have been identified and classified in four subtypes: international organisations from United Nations (UNO), European Union sources, other sources mainly European scope, and Non-profit and University related institutions that produce comparative data. These sources are presented in Figure 3. After the classification, 33 specific sources have been analysed in order to identify the relevant data available for the project (all along its period of length). Thus, each source has been distinguished according to the specific data it provides about the inclusion of migrants, forced displaced people, refugees and vulnerable groups. Such data are sometimes related to one or various databases (which microdata are usually available at), and studies, reports or informs. The period analysed comprises from January 2015 up to December 2019. The results are presented in the following sub-them.

Nevertheless, we have considered that a previous reflection about strengths and limitations of available data are necessary. In order to do it we will follow the United Nations International Organisation of Migration (IOM) considerations that are highlighted in the “Migration Data Portal” regarding forced migration¹⁶. Thus, we summarize some of the key ideas that should be taken into account.

International data for comparative purposes (within RAISD) are basically collected by the European Union (see Figure 3), the International Organisation of Migration (IOM) and the UN Refugee Agency (the so called UNHCR: United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees).

On the one hand, registration of people who arrive or a settled in (official) camps, takes place through a “unified approach” according to UNHCR Handbook for Registration and other procedures¹⁷. It is employed by UNHCR staff as well as governmental and non-governmental partners who operate camps. According to UNHCR (2013) the main providers of data regarding the population of concern to UNHCR are governmental agencies, UNHCR field offices and NGOs. On the other hand, as Zara Sarzin (2017) points out, migration movements (forced or mixed) are mainly “monitored through population movement tracking systems, which provide rough estimates of such population flows. (...) However, such movement tracking systems are subject to caveats including but not limited to: massive population flows that overwhelm capacity; limited access to certain routes and locations due to instability; unwillingness of individuals to provide information when there is no assistance being offered; and political pressures to suppress accurate reporting on IDP movements”. It alludes to irregular migration ruts, or migrants labelled as irregular or clandestine. Asylum seekers often use such via what makes more challenging “the identification of individuals in need of protection”¹⁸.

¹⁶ IOM (2019). *Forced migration or displacement: Data sources and Data strengths & limitations*. Retrieved from: <https://migrationdataportal.org/themes/forced-migration-or-displacement>

¹⁷ Available at <https://www.unhcr.org/publications/operations/4a278ea1d/unhcr-handbook-registration-provisional-release-september-2003-complete.html> Also consult: United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees (UNHCR) (2007). *Operational Standards for Registration and Documentation*. Geneva: UNHCR. Available at: <http://www.refworld.org/docid/4ae9ac8f0.html>

¹⁸ IOM (2019) recommends in this sense alternative sources. See: The Global Migration Group (GMG) (2016). *Handbook for Improving the Production and Use of Migration Data for Development*. The Global Knowledge Partnership on Migration and Development (KNOMAD) Available at https://www.un.org/en/development/desa/population/migration/events/coordination/15/documents/Final%20Handbook%2030.06.16_AS4.pdf

Figure 3 Sources of data classification

As IOM points out data on forcibly displaced people are lacking information on sex and age, what is a main issue regarding the identification of vulnerable groups and its profiling. Besides, there is variability of data, which deepens fundamentally on the collection methods. Some of them are carried on by international organisations and some by

national organisations. Besides, data discrepancies come out when we disaggregate by country of origin or country of asylum. Moreover, data lack of comparability in many cases. The reasons are “inconsistent definitions and methodologies across countries, organisations and movement tracking systems”. With this regard, different agencies have been working on data interoperability and statistical homogenisation. It means that comparability (for instance countries or types of asylum seekers) works within the same source (e.g.: Eurostat), but different sources should not be compared but to highlight the differences between them.

3.1.4.2 United Nation Organisations' data

3.1.4.3 International Organisation for Migration (IOM)

- IOM collects forced migration data through the [Displacement Tracking Matrix](#) (DTM). DTM is a system used to track and monitor displacement (...) active in over 60 countries since 2004, (...) whether on site or en route”. Data is available at the [DTM Data Portal](#) and it is displayed by country or region, and cause of displacement (Natural hazard, Conflict, Other (political or economic reasons), or all of them).
- Besides IOM “collects data on the number of migrants it assisted and resettled to States offering temporary protection or permanent resettlement. An overview of these data can be found in the [Summary of IOM Statistics](#) or in the [IOM Snapshot](#)”. Easily reached at the Migration Data Portal.
- IOM main site: <https://www.iom.int/>; and for publications see. <https://publications.iom.int/> and <https://eea.iom.int/publication>
 - World Migration Report (several years): Latest 2020 <https://eea.iom.int/publications/world-migration-report-2020>
- The [Migration Data Portal](#): most of migration issues are analysed; and updated data is available about forced migration and refugees. Also known as the IOM's Global Migration Data Analysis Centre (GMDAC) Indicators provided are related to: Immigration & emigration, Migrant flow, Vulnerability, Integration & well-being, Forced migration, Development, Migration policy, and, Public opinion.
 - Special themes of interest: “Migration & vulnerability”: Child and young migrants; Forced migration or displacement; Gender and migration; Human trafficking; Migrant deaths and disappearances; Migrant integration; Older persons and migration; and Smuggling of migrants.
 - The main sections of the Portal are:
 - Migration governance: Through projects such as the Migration Governance Indicators (MGI), IOM collects qualitative data on migration governance in a number of countries. Available at: <https://migrationdataportal.org/themes/migration-policies-and-governance>
 - Missing migrants: data on migrants who have passed away or gone missing on migratory routes worldwide. <https://migrationdataportal.org/themes/migrant-deaths-and-disappearances>

- Victims of Human Trafficking and abused migrants: Through its Migrant Assistance Division (MPA), IOM collects data on the victims of human trafficking it assists, anonymizes any personal data, and compiles them in a global database.
<https://migrationdataportal.org/themes/human-trafficking> and The Counter-Trafficking Data Collaborative (CTDC) based on data contributed by counter-trafficking organisations around the world. <https://www.ctdatacollaborative.org/>
- Irregular migrant flows: <https://migrationdataportal.org/themes/irregular-migration> and IOM's Displacement Tracking Matrix (DTM) also provides estimates of irregular migrant flows in certain locations through the flow monitoring system.
- Assisted voluntary return and reintegration (AVRR): Data on IOM's AVRR programmes are collected by the Migrant Protection and Assistance Division (MPA) <https://migrationdataportal.org/themes/return-migration>; <https://www.iom.int/assisted-voluntary-return-and-reintegration> . This includes case data on migrants in vulnerable situations (unaccompanied migrant children, victims of trafficking and migrants with health-related needs), which is not publicly available.
- Migration and health: <https://migrationdataportal.org/themes/migration-and-health> collects data on the physical and mental health of migrants
- Public opinion on migration. <https://migrationdataportal.org/themes/public-opinion-migration>
- Regarding "Forced migration" IOM collects data through the Displacement Tracking Matrix (DTM) <https://displacement.iom.int> . Also consult: <https://migrationdataportal.org/themes/forced-migration-or-displacement>

3.1.4.4 United Nations Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs (UNOCHA)

- The Humanitarian Data Exchange (HDX) is "an open platform for sharing data from a range of partners, which provides 4,915 datasets over 244 locations." The data offers information about: the context in which a humanitarian crisis is occurring; the people affected by the crisis and their needs; and the response by organisations and people seeking to help those who need assistance.¹⁹ Available at <https://data.humdata.org/>

3.1.4.5 UN High Commissioner for Human Rights

- High Commissioner for Human Rights²⁰- Global Migration Group (2016), Principles and Practical Guidance on the Protection of the Human Rights of Migrants in Vulnerable Situations. <https://www.ohchr.org/Documents/Issues/Migration/PrinciplesAndGuidelines.pdf>

¹⁹ Source: UNOCHA (no date) How does HDX define humanitarian data? Retrieved from: <https://data.humdata.org/faq>

²⁰ Also see Report of the United Nations High Commissioner for Human Rights to the Human Rights Council (3 January 2018) UN Doc. A/HRC/37/34

3.1.4.6 UNHCR- UN Refugee Agency

- International policies regarding refugees, stateless people and refugee-like situation are available at its Main website : <https://www.unhcr.org/> Some interesting issues:
 - The Global Compact on Refugees (2018) https://www.unhcr.org/gcr/GCR_English.pdf
 - the Global refugee Forum <https://www.unhcr.org/global-refugee-forum.html>
 - UNHCR Policies
 - [Policy on Age, Gender and Diversity](#) 2018
 - [Joint Strategy - Enhancing Self-Reliance in Food Security and Nutrition in Protracted Refugee Situations](#) 2019
 - [Policy Guide on Entrepreneurship for Migrants and Refugees](#) 2018
 - [Refugee Livelihoods and Economic Inclusion - 2019-2023 Global Strategy Concept Note](#) 2018
 - [A guide to market-based livelihood interventions for refugees](#) 2017
 - [Operational Guidelines on the Minimum Criteria for Livelihoods Programming](#) 2015
- Data: as IOM (2019) describes it “UNHCR collects and provides data on the following types of forcibly displaced persons: refugees (including those in a refugee-like situations), Internally Displaced People (IDPs), asylum seekers, returned refugees, returned IDPs, individuals under UNHCR’s statelessness mandate, and other groups or persons of concern to UNHCR. [UNHCR’s Statistics Database](#) provides data disaggregated by persons of concern, year, country of asylum, origin, gender, age, legal status and resettlement”. “Annually produces six main publications with relevant statistics: [Global Trends: Forced Displacement](#), [Statistical Yearbooks](#), [Mid-Year Trends](#), [Global Appeal](#), and [Global Report](#). It also produces a [statistics technical series](#) of papers. The [United Nations Children’s Fund](#) (UNICEF) presents data from UN DESA and UNHCR relating to migration, including forced migration specific to children. Data are disaggregated by country of asylum”.
 - Statistics topics: persons of concern, time series, demographics, asylum-seekers (refugee status determination), asylum-seekers (monthly data), resettlement, mid-year statistics: http://popstats.unhcr.org/en/overview#_ga=2.37206944.165461678.1572950302-701391545.1570096386 and <https://www.unhcr.org/data.html>
 - Global Trends Report: 2019 at <https://www.unhcr.org/globaltrends2018/> and Statistical Yearbooks <https://www.unhcr.org/statistical-yearbooks.html>
 - Resettlement Data Finder (RDF) https://rsq.unhcr.org/#_ga=2.64946095.165461678.1572950302-701391545.1570096386
 - Operational Portal, countries’ data: <https://data2.unhcr.org/en/countries/>
 - UNHCR WASH Dashboard; infographic database portal visualising current and historical data for the 15 UNHCR Core WASH Indicators. <http://wash.unhcr.org/>
- UNHCR-Regional Representation for Central Europe (RRCE)
 - (outdated) Refugee Integration And The Use Of Indicators: Evidence From Central Europe(2013) http://www.migpolgroup.com/wp_mpg/wp-

[content/uploads/2013/12/Refugee Integration and the use of indicators evidence from central europe CONFERENCE-VERSION.pdf](content/uploads/2013/12/Refugee%20Integration%20and%20the%20use%20of%20indicators%20evidence%20from%20central%20europe%20CONFERENCE-VERSION.pdf)

UN Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs (OCHA)

- ReliefWeb. It is a specialized digital service of OCHA. Countries' reports at: <https://reliefweb.int/countries>

3.1.4.7 European Union's Information and data

- European Union general **policies** on migration:
 - European Commission (Migration and Home Affairs). General information available at: https://ec.europa.eu/home-affairs/what-we-do/policies_en

In the EU territory: Directive 2011/95/EU Recast Qualification Directive; Directive 2013/32/EU Recast Asylum Procedures Directive; Directive 2013/33/EU Recast Reception Conditions Directive; Regulation (EU) No 604/2013 Dublin III Regulation. Regarding financial inclusion see: Directive 2014/92/Eu Of The European Parliament And Of The Council of 23 July 2014 on the comparability of fees related to payment accounts, payment account switching and access to payment accounts with basic features. All available at: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/homepage.html?locale=en>

It is also Worthing: FRA. 2018. Handbook on European non-discrimination law. 2018 edition. Available at http://www.mitramiss.gob.es/oberaxe/ficheros/documentos/fra-2018-handbook-non-discrimination-law-2018_en.pdf

- Common European Asylum System (CEAS) https://ec.europa.eu/home-affairs/what-we-do/policies/asylum_en
- European Agenda on Migration (Brussels, 13.5.2015 COM(2015) 240 final). Available at: <https://ec.europa.eu/home-affairs/what-we-do/policies/european-agenda-migration>
 - European Agenda on Migration four years on: Marked progress needs consolidating in face of volatile situation; "Brussels, 16.10.2019 COM(2019) 481 final Progress report on the Implementation of the European Agenda on Migration": https://ec.europa.eu/home-affairs/sites/homeaffairs/files/what-we-do/policies/european-agenda-migration/20191016_com-2019-481-report_en.pdf
 - Progress information available at: https://ec.europa.eu/home-affairs/news/european-agenda-migration-four-years-marked-progress-needs-consolidating-face-volatile_en Fact sheets available are: Factsheet - Delivering on resettlement; Factsheet - Migration: Solidarity within the EU; Factsheet - Support and solidarity for migration and border management under the EU budget; Factsheet - EU Actions along the Western Mediterranean Route; Factsheet - EU Actions along the Central Mediterranean Route; Factsheet - The EU Facility for Refugees in Turkey; Factsheet - Country Factsheets on financial support to Member States.

- European Commission (2016) The Action Plan on the integration of third-country nationals²¹. Brussels, 7.6.2016 COM(2016) 377 final. Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/home-affairs/what-we-do/policies/legal-migration/integration/action-plan-integration-third-country-nationals_en
 - Factsheet: https://ec.europa.eu/home-affairs/sites/homeaffairs/files/what-we-do/policies/european-agenda-migration/background-information/docs/20160607/factsheet_action_plan_integration_third-country_nationals_en.pdf
 - EU Integration Framework (updated 2019): <https://ec.europa.eu/migrant-integration/public/the-eu-and-integration/framework>
- European Integration Network (EIN)
 - Provides data on specific countries, and mainly comparative policies. As pointed out by the European Commission, it “brings together representatives of national public authorities - mainly from the ministries responsible for migrant integration - from all 28 EU Member States and two EEA countries, Iceland and Norway”²². <https://ec.europa.eu/migrant-integration/main-menu/eus-work/networks>
- European Web Site on Integration (EWSI).
 - Provides different types of information about migrant integration information <https://ec.europa.eu/migrant-integration/resources/documents>; and analysis <https://ec.europa.eu/migrant-integration/analysis>
 - Inclusion of migrants and refugees in cities: https://ec.europa.eu/info/eu-regional-and-urban-development/topics/cities-and-urban-development/priority-themes-eu-cities/inclusion-migrants-and-refugees-cities_en
- The Asylum, Migration and Integration Fund (AMIF):
 - Previously Refugee Fund (2008-2013) and Integration Fund (2007-13). Funds national and transnational projects for integration: https://ec.europa.eu/home-affairs/financing/fundings/migration-asylum-borders/asylum-migration-integration-fund_en
- European Migration Forum (EMF):

²¹ As stated at the EU's main site, the competence on integration lies primarily with the Member States, but EU establishes “measures to provide incentives and support for Member States to promote the integration of third-country nationals residing legally in their territories”. They follow a multi-stakeholder approach where municipalities and regions have a key role.

²² “Many of them have a role in the planning and implementation of dedicated EU funding opportunities, such as the Asylum, Migration and Integration Fund (AMIF), in their respective countries. The 32 members (and 28 alternate members) consult with the European Commission on current developments and policy agenda in the field of integration. They also participate in targeted study visits, peer reviews, workshops and mutual assistance actions on specific integration aspects, with the main aim of exchanging knowledge”. Source: <https://ec.europa.eu/migrant-integration/network/european-integration-network-2>

- It is a platform for dialogue between civil society and the European institutions²³. Annual report Meetings: 4th EMF meeting (March 2018): Towards a more inclusive labour market for migrants: Seizing the potential by addressing the challenges; 3rd EMF meeting (March 2017): Migrants' access to the EU, to rights and to services - Challenges and ways forward; 2nd EMF meeting (April 2016): Long-term approach to sustainable labour migration and successful integration; 1st EMF meeting (January 2015): Safe routes, safe futures. How to manage the mixed flows of migrants across the Mediterranean?
https://ec.europa.eu/home-affairs/what-we-do/policies/legal-migration/european-migration-forum_en
- European Union's Fundamental Rights Agency (FRA)
 - FRA's regular overviews of migration-related fundamental rights concerns are available at: <https://fra.europa.eu/en/theme/asylum-migration-borders/overviews#> Reporting themes are: Key fundamental rights concerns; Situation at the border; Asylum procedure; Return procedure; Reception; Child protection; Immigration detention; Legal, social and policy responses; Hate speech and violent crime.
- The European Asylum Support Office (EASO):
 - It "was set up in 2011 to enhance practical cooperation among Member States on asylum-related matters and for assisting Member States in implementing their obligations under the Common European Asylum System (CEAS)". EASO main site: <https://www.easo.europa.eu/> It provides information about asylum processes ([Quality](#)) and [practical tools for State Members](#)
 - Vulnerable groups considered are: children; and Trafficking in Human Beings. Available at <https://www.easo.europa.eu/asylum-support-training/vulnerable-groups>; and Tool for identification of persons with special needs, available at: <https://ipsn.easo.europa.eu/>
 - Data reports: Latest Asylum trends (<https://www.easo.europa.eu/latest-asylum-trends>) and EASO Annual report on the situation of asylum in the European Union (2014, 2015, 2016, 2017, 2018) (<https://www.easo.europa.eu/easo-annual-report>)
 - Statistics: *Early warning and Preparedness System* (EPS) is a data collection system providing information about the key stages of the Common European Asylum System (CEAS)²⁴.
 - Surveys data base: <https://www.easo.europa.eu/survey-database>
 - Push and pull factors database: <https://www.easo.europa.eu/literature-database>

²³ EESC (no date), retrieved from: <https://www.eesc.europa.eu/en/sections-other-bodies/other/european-migration-forum>

²⁴ For more information see: <https://www.easo.europa.eu/analysis-and-statistics> and Regulation (EC) No 862/2007 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 July 2007 on Community statistics on migration and international protection and repealing Council Regulation (EEC) No 311/76 on the compilation of statistics on foreign workers (Text with EEA relevance). Available at: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex:32007R0862>

- EASO researches: 2018 “A Review of Empirical Surveys of Asylum-Related Migrants” (provisional). Available at: <https://easo.europa.eu/sites/default/files/easo-review-surveys-1-2.pdf>; 2017 “The quantitative assessment of asylum-related migration. A survey of methodologies”; 2016 “The push and pull factors of asylum-related migration. A literature review”
- EASO Consultative Forum with civic society (available at <https://www.easo.europa.eu/civil-society/easo-consultative-forum>). Documents of special interest: 2019 Thematic Meeting on gender-related persecution; 2018 Forum Meeting on Access to Information: Exploring Existing Resources, Good Practices, and Ways Forward.
- Eurostat.
 - Asylum statistics https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php/Asylum_statistics
 - Migration Database: https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php/Migrant_integration_statistics and <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/asylum-and-managed-migration/data/database> Themes presented: Asylum and managed migration (Asylum and Dublin statistic; Enforcement of Immigration Legislation; Residence permits); and Children in migration (asylum and managed migration) (Asylum statistics on children; Residence permits statistics on children; Enforcement of immigration legislation statistics on children).
 - Asylum quarterly report: https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php/Asylum_quarterly_report
 - Migrant integration: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/migrant-integration/data/database>
 - Results of special Eurobarometer 469 on integration of immigrants in the European Union (2018): https://ec.europa.eu/home-affairs/news/results-special-eurobarometer-integration-immigrants-european-union_en
 - The joint EU/Eurostat report, “Indicators of Immigrant Integration” (2011)
- The Knowledge Centre on Migration and Demography (KCMD). It is an European Commission initiative “on better knowledge management for sound EU policy making”²⁵. Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/knowledge4policy/node/6_es
 - The Data Catalogue of the KCMD. Several themes. Available at: <https://bluehub.jrc.ec.europa.eu/catalogues/data/>

²⁵ It supports the European Commission’s overall response to the opportunities and challenges related to migration. It has developed collection of data on migration in general, and in particular on migrant children. See: Schumacher, G., Loeschner, J. and Sermi, F., Data on Children in Migration, Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union (online) doi:10.2760/3048. Available at: <https://ec.europa.eu/jrc/en/publication/data-children-migration>

- It is a metadata catalogue on the following issues: Legal migration and integration; External dimension; Children in migration (<https://ec.europa.eu/jrc/en/publication/data-children-migration>); Migrant smuggling; Irregular migration; Internal displacement; Asylum and refugees (<https://emm.newsbrief.eu/NewsBrief/alertedition/en/Refugees-MigrantCrisis.html>); Demography and migration (such as the “Atlas of Migration” Europe, Data for Integration (D4I) https://ec.europa.eu/knowledge4policy/migration-demography/data-integration-d4i_en#7659 ; International Migration Drivers; Migration Profiles https://ec.europa.eu/knowledge4policy/migration-demography/migration-profiles_en; Data Hub & Tools; https://ec.europa.eu/knowledge4policy/migration-demography_en); Internal EU mobility; Global human mobility; Public sentiment; and Migration governance.
- Data hub: <https://bluehub.jrc.ec.europa.eu/migration/app/>
- Knowledge portal, data catalogue on Asylum and refugees: <https://bluehub.jrc.ec.europa.eu/catalogues/data/group/7asy>
 - Direct link to reports such as: The EASO Annual Report and EASO quarterly report European; Early warning and Preparedness System (EPS) Quarterly Asylum Report dataset (an overview of key asylum trends by analysing data regarding applications for international protection made by asylum seekers; pending cases...); EASO monthly snapshots (Latest Asylum Trends); Western Balkans Quarterly Report; Frontex quarterly and annual reports; Western Balkans Annual Risk Analysis; Eastern Partnership Risk Analysis Network Quarterly Report (EaP-RAN); Eastern European Borders Annual Risk Analysis (EB-RAN); Yearbook on Illegal Migration; Human Smuggling and Trafficking in Central and Eastern Europe; IOM’s Flow Monitoring in the Mediterranean and Western Balkans;
- The Joint Research Centre (JRC Science Hub). It’s the Commission's science and knowledge service. Available at: <https://ec.europa.eu/jrc/en>
 - Special interest publications/themes:
 - European Commission, Joint Research Centre (2019). *Atlas of Migration 2019*, Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union. doi:10.2760/28316 Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/knowledge4policy/sites/know4pol/files/atlas_of_migration_book_final_online.pdf ; Atlas of Migration 2018: <https://ec.europa.eu/jrc/en/publication/atlas-migration-2018>
 - De Haas, Hein. (2018). *European Migrations: Dynamics, Drivers, and the Role of Policies*. Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union, doi:10.2760/168653. Available at: <https://publications.jrc.ec.europa.eu/repository/bitstream/JRC109783/kjna29060enn.pdf>

- Kottmann, A., Vossensteyn, H., Kolster, R., Veidemane, A., Cseres-Gergelyne Blasko, Z., Biagi, F. & Sanchez Barrioluengo, M., (2019). *Social Inclusion Policies in Higher Education: Evidence from the EU*. Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union (online), doi:10.2760/944713. Available at: https://publications.jrc.ec.europa.eu/repository/bitstream/JRC117257/jrc_117257_social_inclusion_policies_in_higher_education_evidence_from_the_eu.pdf
- European Migration Network (EMN)
 - It was established (in 2008) to offer “up-to-date, objective, reliable and comparable information on migration and asylum with a view to supporting policymaking in the European Union. The EMN also aims to inform the general public on migration and asylum”²⁶. It is an EU network of migration and asylum experts coordinated by Directorate-General for Migration and Home Affairs (European Commission). There are National Contact Points (EMN NCPs) in all Member States (except Denmark) and Norway.
 - Reports and data provided: Annual Reports on Migration and Asylum, Studies on relevant topics, Informs, Country Factsheets, Ad-Hoc Queries, the Asylum and Migration Glossary (See Annexe 5), informs on Annual conferences and theme-specific events, and the Bulletin. We highlight the following:
 - EMN Country Fact Sheets. Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/home-affairs/what-we-do/networks/european_migration_network/reports/factsheets_en
 - Special interest: EMN. (2018). [Understanding Migration in the European Union. Insights from the European Migration Network 2008-2018](#). EMN 10 Year Anniversary Report. Brussels: European Migration Network.
 - EMN Studies (several years; several themes). Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/home-affairs/what-we-do/networks/european_migration_network/reports/studies_en
 - Documents of interest: Year 2019: Comparative overview of national protection statuses in the EU and Norway²⁷. Year 2017: The changing influx of asylum seekers in 2014-2016; Approaches to Unaccompanied Minors Following Status Determination; Annual Report on Migration and Asylum EU 2017. Year 2016: Illegal Employment of Third-Country Nationals EU 2016; Returning Rejected Asylum Seekers: challenges and good practices EU 2016; Resettlement and Humanitarian Admission Programmes in Europe EU 2016. Year 2015: Integration of beneficiaries of international protection EU 2015; Policies, practices and data on unaccompanied minors in the EU Member States and Norway Synthesis Report Final 2015.

²⁶ Retrieved from: https://ec.europa.eu/home-affairs/what-we-do/networks/european_migration_network_en

²⁷ EMN. (2019). 2019: Comparative overview of national protection statuses in the EU and Norway. National Contribution from Spain.

Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/home-affairs/sites/homeaffairs/files/26a_spain_national_protection_statuses_final.pdf

- EMN Informs. Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/home-affairs/what-we-do/networks/european_migration_network/reports/informs_en
 - Documents of interest: Year 2019: Inform: Migratory Pathways for Start-ups and Innovative Entrepreneurs in the European Union. Year 2018: Beneficiaries of international protection travelling to their country of origin; Annual Report on Migration and Asylum EU 2018; Labour market integration of third-country nationals in EU member states; Inform: Social Benefits and Rights for Beneficiaries of International Protection; Safe Countries of Origin. Year 2017: The changing influx of asylum seekers in 2014-2016: Member State responses; Approaches to Unaccompanied Minors Following Status Determination; Challenges and practices for establishing the identity of third country nationals in migration procedures EU 2017; Policy Brief: Migrants' movements through the Mediterranean - EU 2017. Year 2016: Resettlement and Humanitarian Admission Programmes in Europe – what works?; Statelessness; Inform: The Return of Rejected Asylum Seekers: Challenges and Good Practices; The Use of Social Media in the Fight Against Migrant Smuggling. Year 2015: Inform: Inform on migrants' movements through the Mediterranean - EU 2015; Policy Brief: Full report accompanying the inform on migrants' movements through the Mediterranean - EU 2015; The Integration of Beneficiaries of International/Humanitarian Protection into the Labour Market: Policies and Good Practices.
- EMN Ad-Hoc Queries (collecting comparative information) (several years; several themes). Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/home-affairs/what-we-do/networks/european_migration_network/reports/adhocqueries_en
 - 2019 Documents of interest: 54. Identifying and counteracting gender-based violence against female asylum seekers; 53. Part II on asylum and improving communication between the authorities and minors; 52. Asylum and improving communication between the authorities and minors; 50. Asylum applications submitted at the border or transit zones; 49. Processing times first instance asylum cases; 46. Venezuelans with expired passports; 44. Language and Communication Policy and Measures in Reception Facilities for Applicants for International Protection; 40. Procedure to Certify Statelessness; 37. Nexus between recognition of stateless status and the right of residence; 36. Refugee Employment Support; 34. Family Reunification of Beneficiaries of International Protection; 28. The status granted to family members of recognized refugees or beneficiaries of subsidiary protection; 25. Administrative or judicial review of appeals against administrative expulsion decisions; 20. Specially commissioned Decision Makers; 17. Border procedures - information to citizens at detention facilities; 15. Early language support; 5. Right to work for asylum seekers; 2. Reasons for being excluded from the grant of international protection and criminal liability for incorrect or incomplete information.

- 2018 Documents of interest: 52. Monitoring Integration; 1344. Issuing a residence permit to rejected asylum seekers without a valid travel document; 1343. Seekers for international protection who lost the right to reside in a state – procedure; 1341. Civic integration policy in relation to recognised refugees; 1334. Asylum Applications from Venezuela; 1332. Ethiopian Asylum Seekers; 1331. Support measures to facilitate the labour market entry of family members; 1320. Free procedural/legal advice/counselling during the administrative asylum procedure; 1309. Identification of victims of human trafficking during asylum interview; 1297. Judicial review of appeals against international protection decisions; 1294. PART II – Reception and Care of Vulnerable Applicants for International Protection with Special Reception Needs; 1292. Part I - Reception of Vulnerable Applicants for International Protection with Special Reception Needs; 1280. International protection to Georgian nationals; 1277. Take charge/take back situation in case asylum application was not yet made; 1276. Evidence on the impact that policy changes on the right to refugee family reunion may have on asylum intake and the number of family reunion applications received; 1273. Recreational activities and leisure equipment in detention; 1272. Detention and material detention conditions; 1270. Unaccompanied Minors – “Volunteer Tutor/Guardian”; 1269. Unaccompanied Minors – “Social Folder”; 1264. Service design/innovation/design thinking best practices within immigration services in Europe; 1262. Use of Cloud Services for Processing Personal Data in Immigration Cases; 1258. Time Limit to reopen Applications (Directive 2013/32/EU); 1257. Experience with granting international protection and returning Sri Lankan nationals to their country of origin; 2017 Documents of interest: 1254. Update of ES AHQ on abuses in requests for Asylum (October 2015); 1252. Updated information on asylum applications by LGBTs and religious converts; 1251. Electronic platform for asylum seekers or their legal aids and representatives; 1249. Access to financial allowances; 1246. Access to healthcare; 1244. Access to education; 1241. Turkish asylum seekers; 1238. Adequate reception arrangements when returning UAMs (unaccompanied minors); 1232. "Welcome Office" for TCNs; 1232a. Return of nationals from safe countries of origin for AT, BE, BG, DE, ES, HR, CZ, FI, FR, HU, IE, LU, MT, NL, RO, SK, SI, UK, NO; 1229. Average cost and average length of reception for asylum seekers; 1216. Social innovations in the field of employment and self-employment of migrants; 1214. Travel documents for asylum seekers; 1212. Legal status of aliens who are subject to the principle of non-refoulement and have been recognized as representing a threat to national security; 1210. Quality Management best practices within the field of asylum decision-making in the first instance; 1204. Impact of false/forged documents in the immigration and asylum procedures; 1202. Documents Identity Fraud Determination Procedure (IFDP); 1199. Unaccompanied asylum-seeking children followed by family members under Dublin Regulation; 1197. Humanitarian Protection; 1195. Appeal procedure and reception conditions after first instance

decision for nationals of safe countries of origin; 1190. Immediate family members applying for asylum at the same time; 1187. Type of International Protection Status for victims of FGM (female genital mutilation); 1186. Implementation of Directive 2008/115/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 16 December 2008 on common standards and procedures in Member States for returning illegally staying third-country nationals; 1181. Providing security to the civil staff, working in the Detention Centre; 1180. Mobile device information; 1174. Policies regarding asylum seekers from Iraq; 1173. Infectious diseases during the international protection procedure; 1172. Claims from Turkish Asylum Seekers; 1171. Palestinians from Gaza and west Union territories; 1169. Terms (and exceptions) for naturalization; 1168. Integration measures regarding language courses and civic integration – Part 2; 1167. Integration measures regarding language courses and civic integration – Part 1; 1163. VIS in return matters (part 2: type D visas and statistics); 1147. Emergency situation in case of mass influx of asylum seekers; 1145. Return of unaccompanied minors; 1143. Assessment of a risk of illegal immigration of the alien may emerge; 1141. Accelerated asylum procedures and asylum procedures at the border (part 2); 1135. Exemption of humanitarian assistance from criminalisation; 1134. Returning Albanian Unaccompanied Asylum Seeking Children; 1132. Transfers to Bulgaria under the Dublin III Regulation; 1131. Processing of asylum applications from nationals of Turkey

- 2016 Documents of interest: 1127. Implementation of the AMIF; 1126. Classification of information related to making and examining an application for international protection; 1125. Immigration Quota Systems and Practices; 1123. Conditions to be granted a residence permit; 1097. The content of integration programmes for applicants for/beneficiaries of international protection; 1096. The waiting period for family reunification for beneficiaries of subsidiary protection; 1093. Functioning of closed type centres for asylum-seekers under the Directive 2013/33/EU; 1091b. Access of international protection applicants to the labour market; 1089. Support networks for newly arrived migrants; 1086. Follow-up to the DE EMN NCP Ad-Hoc Query on allowances for international protection applicants; 1080. Practice in regards to Sunni Arab Muslim asylum seekers from Iraq; 1074. Checking identity and family relationships in case of family reunification with a beneficiary of international protection; 1072. Granting refugee status to applicants claiming to belong to religious minorities; 1071. Rules on family reunification of unaccompanied minors granted refugee status or subsidiary protection; 1068. Interaction between criminal proceedings and asylum procedure; 1067. Joint ad-hoc query COM & LU EMN NCP on statelessness: minors born in exile and unaccompanied minors (part 2); 1066. Joint ad-hoc query COM & LU EMN NCP on statelessness (part 1); 1065. Protection of victims of human trafficking (ONLY for AT, DK, FI, FR, DE, IE, LU, NL, SE, UK and NO); 1061. National asylum policies regarding LGBT-asylum seekers; 1059. Asylum seekers from Libya; 1058. The role of urban areas and small cities in migrants'

settlements patterns: policies and practices; 1057. Article 14 of Directive 2011/95/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 December 2011 on standards for the qualification of third-country nationals or stateless persons as beneficiaries of international protection, for a uniform status for refugees or for persons eligible for subsidiary protection, and for the content of the protection granted; 1055. Addressing and preventing the use of social media in migrant smuggling – exploring cooperation frameworks with social media and other relevant online service providers; 1050. Asylum seekers from Yemen; 1045. Recent practice regarding asylum seekers from Burundi; 1041. Ethical rules of presenting information on the topics of migration and integration; 1040. Violence prevention and sexual education courses to migrants; 1038. Best Practices for Conducting Asylum Interviews; 1037. Best Practices and Methods of Establishing the Identity of Applicants for International Protection; 1034. State Compensation to victims of trafficking in human beings; 1033. Statistical tools, organisational needs and best practices regarding statistics; 1032. Polygamous Marriage; 1028. The application of Sovereignty Clause in Dublin procedure; 1027. Support provided to asylum seekers; 1026. Changes in migration policy in situation of mass migration; 1024. Member States' policies to handle the influx of asylum seekers; 1023. Systems of support persons for beneficiaries of international protection; 1016. Recognition of academic and professional qualification of beneficiaries of international protection.

- 2015 Documents of interest: 1035. Handing over of personal documents in the framework of the asylum and return procedure; 731. Asylum seekers from Iraq; 729. Possible changes in the social security concerning the foreigners with residence permit on the grounds of protection status; 723. Travel documents issued to family members of refugees or other beneficiaries of international protection who do not hold travel documents; 717. The organisation of reception centres; 712. The interpretation of the Article 8 paragraph 2 of the Directive 2011/95/EU (recast Qualification Directive); 699. Reconsidering protection needs; 693. Subsequent asylum applications and re-opened cases; 684. Citizenship status of persons from Western Sahara (Sahrawi citizens); 683. Monitoring integration; 682. Asylum proceeding and returns to Somalia; 678. Asylum seekers from the Russian federation; 677. Palestinian's characterization as "stateless"; 665. Sanctions for holders of an asylum residence permit in case of (proven) identity fraud; 663. Support projects for applicants for international protection; 660. Syrian child brides in the asylum procedure; 659. Concept of safe country of origin in relation to Albania, Kosovo, Macedonia (FYROM), Serbia, Montenegro, Bosnia and Herzegovina; 656. Withdrawing temporary and permanent non-asylum residence permits due to issues of public order; 654. Access to the labour market for asylum seekers.

- European Committee of the Regions (CoR). (2019)

- Regarding migration, the following works are very interesting: “Cities and Regions for Integration initiative”. Available at: <https://ec.europa.eu/migrant-integration/news/eu-committee-of-the-regions-set-to-launch-cities-and-regions-for-integration-initiative>
- (outdated) Study on Practices of Integration of Third-Country Nationals at Local and Regional Level in the European Union(2013): http://cor.europa.eu/en/documentation/studies/Documents/survey_integration_3rd_country_nationals/survey_integration_3rd_country_nationals.pdf

3.1.4.8 Other International Sources

European Resettlement Network.

- It is coordinated by the International Organisation for Migration (IOM), the International Catholic Migration Commission (ICMC) Europe, and the Office of the United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees (UNHCR). At: <http://www.resettlement.eu/>

ESS European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ESS ERIC)

- European Social Survey (several years) (ECA Region); Microdata Available at: <http://www.europeansocialsurvey.org> Topics covered (excluding R1-R5):

Media and social trust	R6 2012	R7 2014	R8 2016	R9 2018
Politics	R6 2012	R7 2014	R8 2016	R9 2018
Subjective well-being...	R6 2012	R7 2014	R8 2016	R9 2018
Gender, Household	R6 2012	R7 2014	R8 2016	R9 2018
Socio demographics	R6 2012	R7 2014	R8 2016	R9 2018
Human values	R6 2012	R7 2014	R8 2016	R9 2018
Immigration		R7 2014		
Timing of life				R9 2018
Personal ... well-being	R6 2012			
Welfare attitudes			R8 2016	
Democracy	R6 2012			
Social inequalities in health		R7 2014		
Justice and Fairness in Europe				R9 2018

Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD):

- Dashboard of indicators for measuring policy and institutional coherence for migration and development. Available at: <http://www.oecd.org/dev/migration-development/knomad-dashboard.htm#Dashboardnew>
- Topics covered: Economic aspects of migration, Integration policies and indicators, Migration and development, Migration policies, Monitoring migration. OECD Databases on Migration <http://www.oecd.org/migration/mig/oecdmigrationdatabases.htm>

OECD International Migration database	Provides tables with recent annual series on migration flows and stocks of foreign-born or foreigners in OECD countries as well as on acquisitions of nationality.
Database on Immigrants in OECD countries (DIOC)	Provides comprehensive and comparative information on a broad range of demographic and labour market characteristics of immigrants living in OECD countries as well as in a number of non-OECD countries (DIOC extended or DIOC-E)
Indicators of Immigrant Integration	Provides a set of indicators of immigrant integration in the fields of employment, education and skills, social inclusion, civic engagement and social cohesion at the national or at the local level.

- Integration. Available at https://www.oecd-ilibrary.org/social-issues-migration-health/making-integration-work_25227726 10 Nov 2017 Making Integration Work; 20 Jun 2017 Making Integration Work: Assessment and Recognition of Foreign Qualifications; 28 Jan 2016 Making Integration Work
- General data. Available at: <http://www.oecd.org/migration/>
- 2019 International Migration and Displacement Trends and Policies. Report to the G20. Available at: <http://www.oecd.org/migration/publicationsdocuments/reports/> :
 - 2019 International Migration and Displacement Trends and Policies. Report to the G20. Available at: <https://www.oecd.org/migration/mig/G20-migration-and-displacement-trends-and-policies-report-2019.pdf>
 - International Migration Outlook 2019. Available at: <http://www.oecd.org/migration/international-migration-outlook-1999124x.htm>
 - 2019 The Road to Integration - Education and Migration. Available at: <http://www.oecd.org/migration/the-road-to-integration-d8ceec5d-en.htm>
 - OECD (2019). *Ready to Help? Improving Resilience of Integration Systems for Refugees and other Vulnerable Migrants*, OECD Publishing, Paris, <https://doi.org/10.1787/9789264311312-en>²⁸. Available at: <https://www.oecd-ilibrary.org/sites/9789264311312-en/index.html?itemId=/content/publication/9789264311312-en>
 - Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development, United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees. 2018. *Safe Pathways For Refugees*. OECD-UNHCR Study on third country solutions for

²⁸ This report looks at ways to improve the resilience of systems to deal with the unexpected arrival of large inflows of refugees and other vulnerable migrants. It begins with an overview of the recent flows of migrants seeking protection, discusses the expected economic impact of these flows, and notes what has been an unprecedented multilateral response. It then examines the process of integrating refugees and other vulnerable migrants, in terms of their economic and social outcomes, as well as specific factors of vulnerability. It also provides a comprehensive assessment of the transition policies in place to support their livelihood in destination and transit countries, as well as in origin countries upon return. Finally, the report tackles issues of anticipation, monitoring and reacting, examining the role of early warning mechanisms and the challenge of improving information so as to better monitor integration outcomes and frame policies.

refugees: family reunification, study programmes and labour mobility. Available at: <http://www.oecd.org/migration/UNHCR-OECD-safe-pathways-for-refugees.pdf>

United Nations Relief and Works Agency for Palestine refugees in the Near East (UNRWA):

- Produces information on Middle East. The Agency provides assistance for Palestinian refugees in Gaza, Jordan, Lebanon, Syria, the West Bank and the Gaza Strip. <https://www.unrwa.org/> Publications related to statistics are available at: <https://www.unrwa.org/resources/reports>

3.1.4.9 Data from Non-profit and University related institutions

European Council on Refugees and Exiles (ECRE):

- It is an alliance of 104 NGOs across 41 European countries <https://www.ecre.org/> It manages 'The Asylum Information Database' (AIDA):
 - It is a database on asylum procedures, reception conditions, detention and other content. It is an initiative "Mapping asylum procedures, reception conditions, detention and content of protection in Europe" <https://www.asylumineurope.org/>
 - AIDA Country reports (2019) available at: https://ec.europa.eu/home-affairs/what-we-do/networks/european_migration_network/reports/factsheets_en
 - Comparative reports at <https://www.asylumineurope.org/comparative-reports>. Themes presented: Asylum authorities: An overview of internal structures and available resources (2019); Housing out of reach? The reception of refugees and asylum seekers in Europe, (2019); Access to protection in Europe: The registration of asylum applications (2018); Access to protection in Europe: Borders and entry into the territory (2018); Boundaries of Liberty: Asylum and de facto detention in Europe (2018); **The concept of vulnerability in European asylum procedures** (2017)²⁹; Refugee rights subsiding? Europe's two-tier protection regime and its effect on the rights of beneficiaries (2017); Admissibility, responsibility and safety in European asylum procedures (2017); Wrong counts and closing doors: The reception of refugees and asylum seekers in Europe, (2016); Common asylum system at a turning point: Refugees caught in Europe's solidarity crisis (2015).

²⁹ Available at: http://www.asylumineurope.org/sites/default/files/shadow-reports/aida_vulnerability_in_asylum_procedures.pdf

Emmy-Noether program of the German Research Foundation:

- The IMPIC Project- Immigration Policies in Comparison (2011-2016). Available at: <http://www.impic-project.eu/>

European Program for Integration and Migration <https://www.epim.info>

- It is a collaborative funding initiative of currently twenty-five grant-making foundations, hosted in the Network of European Foundations (NEF). EU Policy updates: <https://www.epim.info/publications/> Themes: Migration and Detention; Reforming the Common European Asylum System; Children and Youth on the Move, (4) Mobile EU Citizens' Access to Rights, and (5) Building Inclusive European Societies. (latest update dec.2019: <https://www.epim.info/wp-content/uploads/2019/12/EPIM-Policy-Update-December19.pdf> see Stateless Inclusion)

Global Migration Group

- Migration Policy Group and Institute of Public Affairs (2019) the European Benchmark for refugee integration: a comparative analysis of the national integration evaluation mechanism in 14 European countries <https://www.migpolgroup.com/wp-content/uploads/2019/06/The-European-benchmark-for-refugee-integration.pdf>

Migrant Integration Policy Index (MIPEX)

- Multiple-partners project co-funded by the European Commission and IOM (among others). Measures policies to integrate migrants in all EU Member States, Australia, Canada, Iceland, Japan, South Korea, New Zealand, Norway, Switzerland, Turkey and the USA. (Citation: Migrant Integration Policy Index 2015. Huddleston, Thomas; Bilgili, Ozge; Joki, Anne-Linde and Vankova, Zvezda) Data available at: <http://www.mipex.eu/what-is-mipex>

Migration Institute (University of Amsterdam).

- In 2017, IMI ceased to operate as an institute at the University of Oxford and became an international network (IMI-n). From 2019, IMI has been part of the Amsterdam Institute for Social Science Research (AISSR) at the University of Amsterdam. DEMIG POLICY data works on Determinants of International Migration. Available at: <https://www.migrationinstitute.org/data/demig-data/demig-policy-1> Database:
 - DEMIG (2015) DEMIG POLICY, version 1.3, Online Edition. Oxford: International Migration Institute, University of Oxford. www.migrationdeterminants.eu

Migration Policy Institute (2014-2019).

- MPI- Europe. Nonprofit, independent research institute that aims to provide a better understanding of migration in Europe and thus promote effective policymaking.
- International Migration Statistics. Topics covered: Immigrants, Emigrants, and Net Migration, Humanitarian Migration (Refugees and Asylum Seekers), Trends over Time, Global Remittances.

Available at: <https://www.migrationpolicy.org> & <https://www.migrationpolicy.org/programs/mpi-europe>

- The Migration Information Source (online journal). Available at: <https://www.migrationpolicy.org/programs/migration-information-source>

National Integration Evaluation Mechanism (NIEM PROJECT)

- It is a six-years long transnational project which aims to prepare key actors in the integration field in 15 EU Member States. Co-funded by the Foundation Open Society Institute, the Asylum, Migration and Integration, and the International Visegrad Fund. Publication of interest: <http://www.forintegration.eu/pl/pub>
 - The European benchmark for refugee integration: The report presents a comparative, indicator-based assessment of the refugee integration frameworks in place in 14 countries: Czechia, France, Greece, Hungary, Italy, Latvia, Lithuania, the Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovenia, Spain and Sweden.
 - National Reports 2018
 - Migration in the Mediterranean. The challenge between Africa and Europe
 - New asylum recast may undermine the EU's. Greatest impact on refugee integration
 - Lost in transition? The European standards behind refugee integration

The International Migration Policy and Law Analysis (IMPALA) Database.

- Is a cross-national, cross-institutional, cross-disciplinary project on comparative immigration policy. A collaborative project of Harvard University, the University of Luxembourg, the University of Amsterdam, the London School of Economics, and the University of Sydney. Available at: <http://www.impaladatabase.org/>

TRACKS-project (2016-2018) (HOME/2014/AMIF/AG/ASYL/7849)

- Transnational project identification of TRafficked Asylum seeKers' Special needs coordinated by Forum Réfugiés - Cosi (FR). General information at: https://ec.europa.eu/knowledge4policy/projects-activities/tracks-identification-trafficked-asylum-seekers-special-needs_en Final report "Identification and response to the needs of Trafficked Asylum Seekers. A Comparative Report For The Republic Of Cyprus, France, Ireland, Italy, Spain, The UK and Switzerland" at: <https://www.cear.es/wp-content/uploads/2018/03/TRACKS-consolidated-Report-January-2018.pdf>

The Platform for International Cooperation on Undocumented Migrants (PICUM): <https://picum.org/>

- Its focus areas are: health care, labour, housing, detention and return, children and youth, access to justice and women

3.2 Analytical procedures and evaluation techniques for deliverables

3.2.1 Introduction

After fieldwork we have begun to the characterisation of Vulnerable Groups (VGs) among Forcibly Displaced People (FDP), their characteristics, challenges and needs; and we are also proceeding to the identification of attention and inclusion practices.

Our departure point in RAISD is that Institutions and organisations put in practice different strategies for the attention, reception, settlement and integration of migrants with heterogeneous results.

They usually disregard information that depicts a complex and heterogeneous migration landscape, where needs of vulnerable groups are unknown and/or mismatched.

Thus, we want to analyse a social setting in a holistic way, at different levels of abstraction and from different perspectives.

The definition and **identification of vulnerable groups**, and the “**vulnerability context**” concept” (VCs) and the description of both constitute the first specific objective (SO1).

It is related to Work Packaged WP4: **Vulnerability profiling**, and its leader is Anadolu University (AU).

It includes both discovering the kind of information that should characterise such contexts and identifying actual ones in recent and current forcibly displaced persons’ (FDP) situations.

D4.1 Vulnerability context: definition and guidelines – preliminary version (AU, April 2020).

Later on (2021) RAISD will generate:

D4.2 AU: Vulnerability context definition & Guidelines.

D4.3. UH: Catalogue of Vulnerability context.

According to the information collected throughout the fieldwork the project will have data enough to map (and later to assess) how different practices, policies, laws and treaties are affecting attention and inclusion strategies towards vulnerable groups among the forcibly displaced.

This is related to the next objectives of RAISD: SO2 *Identification of attention and inclusion practices for Vulnerable Groups (VGs) of Forcibly Displaced People (FDP)* and R2.1. Catalogue of current attention and inclusion practices related to Vulnerable Groups of Forcibly Displaced.

The latter is also related to Work Package WP5: Design of tailored attention and inclusion strategies.

Its leader is Ménedek, and the first expected deliverable is by LIU:

D5.1 Catalogue of attention and inclusion practices for FDP in the EU influence area, by Lebanese International University (LIU, February 2020).

In parallel the University of Helsinki (UH) is Leading Work Package 7, **Cross analysis**. On the evaluation criteria for attention and inclusion practices in different VCs. It will start with the criteria used by different types of stakeholders in those contexts. Then, it will work on integrated evaluation criteria, able to provide a single evaluation from the actor-oriented criteria. The integrated criteria will be applied only to VCs and TAISs. This task will work on the information provided by previous works and i will request frequent feedback to and from ARUs to validate its work.

Thus, UH is working at the same time with the produced data on:

D7.3 Evaluation criteria: actor-oriented and integrated evaluation – preliminary version (D7.4 final version) (UH, January 2020).

WP7 integrates the different sources of feedback of the project results, where it performs a cross-analysis to provide a coherent landscape to the other WPs. This will incorporate the results from the ARU pilots.

Therefore, in RAISD all **data produced in the fieldwork -and throughout the project- is treated and analysed from different perspectives** in order to produce unique analytical and practical products (different Milestones and Deliverables).

3.2.2 Preliminary analysis process

3.2.2.1 Participatory feedback and ARU's contribution

As already pointed out, **data is produced repeatedly within the ARUs** all along the projects' processes and duration. Thus, **Work Package Leaders must have an active role planning and designing tools** for each task.

Action Research Units members (and other stakeholders) contribute to:

- Discuss the research design, the identification of potential VGs, the interviews guidelines/ script.
- Contribute with empirical data in the fieldwork, which includes mapping and identify attention and inclusion practices that are addressed for those vulnerable groups.
- Get involved in the participatory assessment to preliminary results of the fieldworks to contribute to its analysis.
- Identify and create the criteria and the mapping to match vulnerable groups and their needs with suitable practices. Thus, they discuss criteria about what and why a good practice is considered as such, in a certain territory and for certain vulnerable groups.
- Debate criteria to evaluate attention and inclusion practices in different vulnerable contexts.
- Moreover, they will set up and test the TAISs for their VCs and provide the relevant feedback.

Therefore, they must feel highly involved. The creation of Action Research Units (ARUS) is key to the success of other related WPs.

As we already pointed out, strategies to follow are twofold: Individual presentations of main results, and workshops and/or focus groups within each ARU where results are presented and discussed.

Stakeholders involvement also helps to the **credibility and trustworthiness** (Lincoln & Guba, 1985) of the research as it implies the corroboration of data analysis with the some of the participants themselves.

3.2.2.2 Characteristics of qualitative analysis

To characterise qualitative analysis³⁰, we will follow Saldaña's handbook titled *Fundamentals of qualitative research*. Saldaña (2011) explains the characteristics of qualitative analysis:

Since qualitative research design, fieldwork, and data collection are most often provisional, emergent, and evolutionary processes, you reflect on and analyze the data as you gather them and proceed throughout the project. If preplanned methods are not working, you change them to secure the data you need. There is generally a post-fieldwork period when continued reflection and more systematic data analysis occur, concurrent with or followed by additional data collection, if needed, and the more formal write-up of the study, which is in itself an analytic act. (pp. 90)

That is why so many authors refer to qualitative analysis as a “craft” and an open process.

As Saldaña states, **credibility and trustworthiness** (following Lincoln & Guba, 1985) are two key terms regarding quality in qualitative data, while “reliability and validity are terms and constructs of the positivist quantitative paradigm that refer to the replicability and accuracy of measures” (2011, 134). Both concepts are related to the clarity and systematization of the methodology (number of researchers, number of interviews, techniques of gathering information, Interview transcripts systems, analytical model...), that able the audience of the document to consider its trustiness. “The bottom line is that credibility and trustworthiness are matters of researcher honesty and integrity. Anyone can write that he worked ethically, rigorously, and reflexively” (2011, 90).

Quality is also related to richly descriptions of facts and experiences collected throughout the fieldwork, as well as triangulation of data sources: literature and statistics for supporting and illustrating points, (“convergences, complementarities or divergences in the narratives produced by the different sources of data”), (Erzberger & Prein, 1997)³¹.

In RAIS our procedures are described in the **Methodology Guidelines** and the set of **Fieldwork reports** that detailed: literature review, stakeholders' involvement and interviews.

³⁰ For further references see Flick, U. (ed) (2014). *The SAGE Handbook of Qualitative Data Analysis*. Sage. DOI: <https://dx.doi.org/10.4135/9781446282243>; Saldaña, J. (2011). *Fundamentals of qualitative research*. Cary: Oxford University Press. Retrieved from <https://ebookcentral.proquest.com>; Saldaña, J. (2013). *The Coding Manual for Qualitative Researchers* (2nd edition). London: Sage; Schutt, Russell K. (2015) *Qualitative Data Analysis* (Chapter 10), Investigating the Social World: The Process and Practice of Research. 8th Edition. Hampshire: Sage. Retrieved from https://www.sagepub.com/sites/default/files/upm-binaries/43454_10.pdf

³¹ For further details see Erzberger, C. & Prein, G. (1997). Triangulation: Validity and empirically-based hypothesis construction, Quality & Quantity. *International Journal of Methodology*, 1997, vol. 31, issue 2, 141-154. <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1023%2FA%3A1004249313062>

Besides, data analysis is also **triangulated** as it is analysed by at least two teams: each country team plus the Work Package leader in charge of a deliverable.

Categorizing is the key process of qualitative analysis. It involves the “organizing and ordering the vast array of data from a study because it is from these larger and meaning-rich units that we can better grasp the particular features of each one, and the categories’ possible interrelationships with one another” (Saldaña 2011, 91).

Interrelation and interplay appear at a second phase. It is necessary to “explore the ways our patterns and categories interact and interplay “(...) It refers to the structural and processual nature of categories —for example, whether some type of sequential order, hierarchy, or taxonomy exists, whether any overlaps occur, whether there is superordinate and subordinate arrangement, and what types of organisational frameworks or networks might exist among them. There can even be patterns of patterns and categories of categories if your mind thinks conceptually and abstractly enough” (Saldaña, 2011, 92).

3.2.2.3 Codification and other procedures

According to Saldaña (2011) “**coding** is a heuristic — a method of discovery — to the meanings of individual sections of data” (pp.95). These codes function as a way of patterning, classifying, and later reorganizing each datum into emergent categories for further analysis. Different types of codes exist for different types of genres and analytic approaches” (...) “A code in qualitative data analysis is most often a word or short phrase that symbolically assigns a summative, salient, essence-capturing, and/or evocative attribute for a portion of (...) data” (pp. 96).

Qualitative analysis employs the concepts of “themes”, “categories”, and “codes”. As Denise O’Neil Green points out “If one were to think about a micro-, meso-, or macro-level analysis, coding starts at the micro level, the generation of categories moves the investigator to the meso level, and themes that bear out lessons learned or truths that reflect the findings are indicative of a macro-level analysis” (2008, 71).

Saldaña describes the process as follows: “For initial analysis, descriptive codes are clustered into similar categories to detect such patterns as frequency (i.e., categories with the largest number of codes), interrelationship (i.e., categories that seem to connect in some way), and initial work for grounded theory development” (pp. 104).

In the case of RAISD preliminary coding, categories and themes are established deductively, they are based on literature (socio-ecological framework) and mostly from the research questions of the project. Therefore, we assume that at a first, our coding procedure is theoretical.

Thus, the departure point for the analysis is the theoretical codes and **categories set up by the socio-ecological dimensions**. Thus, the codes used by the individual country reports of the fieldwork are:

Theoretical coding is limited because the researchers don't know what more they will find on the field. That is the reason we also employ "*in-vivo coding*".

Saldaña (2011, 99) considers that it *in-vivo coding* "refers to a code based on the actual language used by the participant" (...) he recommends that "in vivo codes be placed in quotation marks as a way of designating that the code is extracted directly from the data record."

From a different perspective, with this regard its analytical origin, codes could be identified as (2011, 104-108):

- Descriptive codes (Miles & Huberman, 1994) are primarily nouns that simply summarize the topic of a datum.
- Values coding (LeCompte & Preissle, 1993; Saldaña, 2009) identifies the values, attitudes, and beliefs of a participant, as shared by the individual and/or interpreted by the analyst.
- Dramaturgical coding (Berg, 2001; Feldman, 1995; Goffman, 1959; Saldaña, 2005) analyze the characters in action, reaction, and interaction. (...) It examines their *objectives* (OBJ) or wants, needs, and motives; the *conflicts* (CON) or obstacles they face as they try to achieve their objectives; the *tactics* (TAC) or strategies they employ to reach their objectives; their *attitudes* (ATT) toward others and their given circumstances; the particular *emotions* (EMO) they experience throughout; and their *subtexts* (SUB) or underlying and unspoken thoughts (2011, 106).
- Versus coding (Hager, Maier, O'Hara, Ott, & Saldaña, 2000; Wolcott, 2003) identifies the conflicts, struggles, and power issues observed in social action, reaction, and interaction as an X VS. Y code, such as: men vs women.
- Analytic Memos — "Think Pieces". "Like field notes writing, perspectives vary among practitioners as to the methods for documenting the researcher's analytic insights and subjective experiences" (2011, 98). (free reflexive thinking).

Themes. Regarding, *themeying the data*, Saldaña (2011, 108) considers that, "unlike codes, which are most often single words or short phrases that symbolically represent a datum, themes are extended phrases or sentences that summarize the manifest (apparent) and latent (underlying) meanings of data (Auerbach & Silverstein, 2003; Boyatzis, 1998). Themes, too, can be categorized, or listed in superordinate and subordinate outline formats as an analytic tactic. (...) A second approach is to categorize the themes into similar clusters and to develop different category labels or *theoretical constructs*" (2011, 109).

Seeking patterns across data and examining relationships and displaying data are both parallel procedures³².

This task could be considered preliminary for each partner as it is an expected outcome of the Tasks Leaders of each deliverable: AU, LIU, and UH

³² Some recommended bibliography for this process of analysis: Bazeley, P. (2013). *Comparative analyses as a means of furthering analysis* (chapter 9, pp. 254-281). Qualitative Data Analysis: Practical strategies. London: Sage.

Miles, M. B., & Huberman, A. M. (1994). *Making Good Sense: Drawing and Verifying Conclusions* (Chapter 10, pp. 245-262). Qualitative Data Analysis: An Expanded Sourcebook (2nd ed.,). Thousand Oaks: Sage.

Leech, Nancy L; Onwuegbuzie, Anthony J. (2011) Beyond Constant Comparison Qualitative Data Analysis: Using NVivo *Psychology Quarterly* 26(1), 70–84.

Thus, cross-case analysis (Miles & Huberman, 1994) is necessary to establish generalisations and for theoretical elaboration. Nowadays in order to look for interactions and relationships software tools are indispensable.

CAQDAS is the acronym we use for Computer Assisted Qualitative Data Analysis Software.

Two software are the most popular employed in social research:

- Atlas.ti (www.atlasti.com)
- NVivo (<https://www.qsrinternational.com/nvivo/home>)

Next step for qualitative analysis is **Conceptualisation**. It is a final step of qualitative analysis. An outcome necessary for theoretical development.

Saldaña (2011, 111) defines conceptualisation as “abstractions that have more meaning to life outside the study” (...) When the concepts of your study have been developed from your codes, categories, and/or themes, they become material for the potential construction of theory “.

Finally, **theorisation** is the most complicated level of analysis. A theory “(as it is traditionally conceived): predicts and controls action through an if/then logic, explains how and/or why something happens by stating its cause(s), provides insights and guidance for improving social life” (Saldaña, 2011, 114).

3.2.3 Report Writing and further steps

Two fieldwork report templates³³ are provided (A and B, as below). Both are tools for the arrangement of the information obtained throughout the fieldwork in each country. Thus, both reports provide information about:

- Detailed description of migration situations of VGs (it will be used for detailed classification of migration situations of VGs and highly vulnerable groups profiling).
- Opportunities and challenges for displaced people.
- Opportunities and challenges for hosting communities' regarding the inclusion of VGs.
- Potential for and resistance to the integration of displaced persons (regarding host communities).
- Effects of migration on social systems.
- Access to and impact on labour markets.
- Cultural integration of third country nationals.
- Institutional (or other's agents) attention and inclusion practices.
- Public and local engagement initiatives.
- Identification of practices (unsuitable or highly recommended) and solutions to ease the pressure on hosting communities.

A. "Synthesis Report about vulnerability profiling & Vulnerability Contexts" Index is showed in the following:

1. Context of arrival: host society.
 - 1.1 Characteristics of the hosting community.
 - 1.2 Immigration and migration flows in the territory.
 - 1.3 Characterisation.
 - 1.4 Migrants' impact on the territory & perceived consequences.
 - 1.5 Social perception of migrants and practices (inclusion/discrimination).
 - 1.5.1 Perception, stereotypes, prejudices, discrimination practices.
 - 1.5.2 Civil society & migrants' rights. migrant's organisations active in the territory. Relations among them.
2. Context of arrival: Policies.
 - 2.1 Role of international organisations and border agreements.
 - 2.2 National government policies.
 - 2.2.1 Formal policies.
 - 2.2.2 Policies regarding social welfare and development.
 - 2.2.3 Policies regarding migration.
 - 2.2.4 Roles and practices of institutions.
 - 2.3 Regional and Local perspective.
3. Vulnerable Groups and related profiles' identification.

³³ Country Report Template contributing to D4.1 "Synthesis Report about vulnerability profiling & Vulnerability Contexts" (UCM, October 2019, v2.), and Country Report Template contributing to D5.1. "Report: Preliminary catalogue of good (attention and inclusion) practices" (UCM, October 2019, v2.).

- 3.1 VGs description.
- 3.2 Difficulties experienced by them in transit.
- 3.3 Arrival: history in this territory/context (of each group).
- 3.4 “Highly” Vulnerable among the Forcibly Displaced: Specific challenges and needs.
 - 3.4.1 Current situation of unaccompanied minors, children, women victims of human trafficking, and people with disabilities.
 - 3.4.2 Current situation of the other VGs identified.
 - 3.4.3 Experiences by VGs at the processes of inclusion in host environments.
- 3.5 Interaction & Difficulties.
 - 3.5.1 Civil society & migrants’ rights: types of interactions and experiences with VG.
 - 3.5.2 Perception of barriers or opportunities for inclusion at present settlement.
- 3.6 Future expectations.

4 VGs’ experiences lived through specific migrants’ or refugees’ programs.

5 Approximation to the Definition of Vulnerable Context (VC).

B. Template “Report: Preliminary catalogue of good (attention and inclusion) practices (D5.1)”, with the following contents:

- 1. Policies, laws and treaties affecting attention and inclusion strategies towards VGs of FDP.
 - 1.1 Policies regarding VGs.
 - 1.2 Implementation of the strategies and policies.
 - 1.3 Formal and Informal care practices from the host or transit communities.
 - 1.4 VGs’ experiences.
 - 1.5 Other stakeholders’ experiences.
- 2. Identification of potential key criteria to evaluate strategies and practices for attention and inclusion of VGs of FDP.
 - 2.1. Actor-oriented criteria to evaluate policies and practices of attention towards Vulnerable Groups (VGs) of forcibly displaced people (FDP).
 - 2.2. Common features for compatible criteria.
- 3. Identification of potential good practices.
 - 3.1. Characterisation of practices.
 - 3.1.1. VG1 name. Practice 1: title.
 - 3.1.2. VG1 name. Practice n: title.
 - 3.2. Formal and informal Practices to be avoided.

3.2.4 Identification of good attention and inclusion practices

3.2.4.1 Definition and basic sources

The aim of this section is to provide a depth analytical input regarding attention and inclusion practices in order to make a progress to the design of the expected tailored practices of RAISD, the so called TAIS.

The template proposed a set of initial criteria for a good practice description:

- Identification of stakeholders that made an identification of the practice.
- Criteria actors or stakeholder are using to assess them as a “good practice”.
- Name and leading organisation (contact details provided).
- Target VG and type of host community.
- Application setting: context.
- Objectives.
- Length.
- Requirements/ accessibility issues.
- Performance procedures.
- Difficulties or constraints for its implementation.
- Results.
- Comments.

Conceptualisation in this scope faces the same challenges as in the rest of the project. Information sources (see section 3.1.4) are: vulnerable people themselves (through interviews), stakeholders (within the ARU or outside it), and literature review. Nevertheless, it is each ARU who must discuss and provide the actors’ criteria to help to identify what *a good practice* is, and what criteria is used for considering it so.

Remember that this information has been mainly produced through the fieldwork. Information provided by **highly vulnerable groups** of forcibly displaced people have been transcribed and it has been available to all partners in NextCloud, and they have been also asked about it. Thus, **Stakeholder** information could have taken different types of sub-sources:

- ARU workshops or meetings.
- Interviews.
- Stakeholders publications or reports (it could be considered as part of the literature review).

We are adopting the **actor-oriented criteria**. It means that RAISD is expected to gain in-depth knowledge on **What good** does mean for the different stakeholders that take part in the project, according to the quintuple helix approach.

Therefore, specific **work must be developed within each ARU** for the identification and discussion of practices:

- Discussing principles, standards, norms, values... What principles, standards, norms, values are named and identify by each type of stakeholder?
- What practices really meet what VGs' needs?
- What and where are the differences?
- What are the common features?

Identification of interesting or (more practices) Good Practices

Figure 5 Example: Max-Neef's Fundamental human needs

Meanwhile a **Basic information collection sheet** was designed and titled “Recognizing and rescuing practices of interest for the care and inclusion of forcibly displaced persons in Spain”.

It was launched to all the participants in our stakeholders' database, especially ARU members. In parallel, literature was reviewed. *Basic information collection sheet* content reproduced the provided template, preceded by a motivation letter:

"The following document wants to contribute to the recognition of social, cultural and educational intervention practices that favour the attention and inclusion of people who belong to especially vulnerable groups among people who arrive in Spain as forcibly displaced persons. In the daily life of our interventions, sometimes small activities or forms of attention go unnoticed, or are not systematized, and we do not usually have the opportunity to explain and disseminate them. We want to pay attention to the content, the meaning, the know-how, and the experiences and knowledge of the intervention."

Requested Information:

- What is your organisation?
- Basic Data of your organisation
- Who can we contact if we want to know more about this experience, and where?
- What name would you give your practice?
- Does it belong to any project? Can you give us more information?
- Who do you perform practice with, who are the beneficiaries?
- What are your main needs and vulnerabilities?
- Application context: objectives, duration.
- Accessibility requirements.
- Performance procedures, ways of carrying it out.
- Principles of action, and values.
- Difficulties or limitations for its implementation.
- Results obtained.
- Comments.

3.2.4.2 Good Practices databases

Data regarding interesting or good practices related to the inclusion and attention of highly vulnerable groups among forcibly displaced people have been collected throughout the fieldwork. Beyond that, there are currently other interesting sources of information on good practices in the inclusion of migrants and refugees.

From a **comparative perspective, and at an international level**, there has been an important institutional effort to publicize good practices in the field of social inclusion over the last few years, especially after the European Agenda on Migration (2016) and The Action Plan on the integration of third-country national. It is also possible to appreciate this very same effort by UNHCR and the International Organisation for Migration (OIM), especially from the momentum of the Global Compact initiative (2018) and further on. RAISD partners should look at these sources in order to enrich their current raw data.

With this regard, UCM has identified and made a preliminary analysis of sources for the next tasks and deliverables of the RAISD project that collect national and international experiences of high interest:

- Assembly of European Regions
 - AER members share their knowledge to improve situation for refugees in their regions and best practices. <https://aer.eu/aer-members-deal-refugees-mutual-learning/>
- Inclusion Project (2016-3-ES02-KA205-008851)
 - Best practices and conclusions from Inclusion European Project. <https://drive.google.com/file/d/1kvPjYtUhnV4cSAag8yZFckmpgL2brh8k/view>
- Education International
 - A Global Union Federation that represents organisations of teachers and other education employees. The specific web “Teachers for migrants’ and refugees’ rights” provides best practices: <https://www.education4refugees.org/best-practices>
- European Asylum Support Office (EASO).
 - EASO. 2018. Briefing Paper Access to Information in the Context of Asylum: Exploring Existing Resources, Good Practices and Ways Forward. <https://www.easo.europa.eu/sites/default/files/EASO-Briefing-Paper-Access-to%20Information--in-the-context-of-Asylum.pdf>
 - EASO Thematic Consultative Forum Meeting on “Access to Information: Exploring Existing Resources, Good Practices, and Ways Forward”, 28 March 2018, Malta. Final report of the meeting: <https://www.easo.europa.eu/sites/default/files/CF-Thematic-Meeting-Report-Final.pdf>
- European Migration Network
 - EMN Ad-Hoc Queries (collecting comparative information). https://ec.europa.eu/home-affairs/what-we-do/networks/european_migration_network/reports/adhocqueries_en
 - Year 2018: 1292. Part I - Reception of Vulnerable Applicants for International Protection with Special Reception Needs; 1294. PART II – Reception and Care of Vulnerable Applicants for

International Protection with Special Reception Needs; 1264. Service design/innovation/design thinking best practices within immigration services in Europe (year 2017): 1210. Quality Management best practices within the field of asylum decision-making in the first instance;

- Year 2016: 1038. Best Practices for Conducting Asylum Interviews; 1037. Best Practices and Methods of Establishing the Identity of Applicants for International Protection; 1034. State Compensation to victims of trafficking in human beings; 1033. Statistical tools, organisational needs and best practices regarding statistics.
- European Web Site on Integration (EWSI) (European Commission):
 - Migrant Integration Information and good practices data base. <https://ec.europa.eu/migrant-integration/main-menu/eus-work/archive/actions>

Studies of interest:

(2015) The Integration of Beneficiaries of International/Humanitarian Protection into the Labour Market: Policies and Good Practices. [Synthesis report](#).

(2016) [Returning Rejected Asylum Seekers: challenges and good practices](#) (in the EU)

- Inclusion of migrants and refugees in cities. Project examples in the web site:
 - [City GROW](#)
The project, funded under the Asylum, Migration and Integration Fund, supports city-to-city mentoring between 16 European cities on several aspects of integration.
 - [Establishment of the Multi-cultural Educational and Care Centre \(MOZC\)](#)
The ERDF co-funded the establishment of a Multi-functional Educational – and Care Centre in Malburgen, the Netherlands.
 - [European Voluntary Service \(EVS\)](#)
The European Voluntary Service helps to mobilise networks targeting teachers, youth workers, school leaders, local authorities and civil society organisations to share concrete practices for the integration of refugees.
 - [GEMM: Growth, Equal Opportunities, Migration and Markets](#)
GEMM analyses the obstacles to the successful incorporation of migrants and assesses the migration-related drivers of growth and ethnic inequality in the labour market as a barrier to competitiveness and innovation in EU countries.
 - [Projects in the field of education](#)
Projects funded under Erasmus+ in the field of education for migrants.
 - [Repository of promising practices of labour market integration of refugees](#)
Repository of promising practices of labour market integration and social inclusion of asylum seekers and refugees across EU countries.

- [Research & innovation projects on migration and mobility](#)
The publication presents an overview of past and ongoing research projects in the areas of migrants' integration, trans-nationalism, temporary/circular migration, gender relations, migration and development, data on flows and statistical modelling, diversity, and economic impact of immigration.
- [Robinsbalje, Bremen's learning neighbourhood](#)
Robinsbalje, a former car park in a deprived neighbourhood, was transformed into a centre which offers education, health and employment services in one facility.
- [Science4Refugees](#)
Science4Refugees aims to help refugee scientists and researchers find suitable jobs that both improve their own situation and put their skills and experience to good use in Europe's research system.
- [Urban Innovative Actions](#)
Innovative solutions for sustainable urban development in Barcelona, Birmingham, Lille, Nantes, Pozzuoli, Turin.
- Other local projects on integration can be found on the [European Website for Integration](#) EWSI.
- European Commission. Others:
 - Repository of promising practices of labour market integration and social inclusion of asylum seekers and refugees across EU Member States.
<https://ec.europa.eu/social/main.jsp?langId=en&catId=1208>
 - European Parliament study, 'Comparative Study on the best practices for the integration of resettled refugees in the EU Member States'(2013).
[http://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/etudes/join/2013/474393/IPOL-LIBE_ET\(2013\)474393_EN.pdf](http://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/etudes/join/2013/474393/IPOL-LIBE_ET(2013)474393_EN.pdf)
 - DG Education and Culture of the European Commission (2009) Mapping of good practices relating to social inclusion of migrants through sport. <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/f1174f30-7975-11e6-b076-01aa75ed71a1/language-en>
- National Integration Evaluation Mechanism (NIEM PROJECT)
 - [The European benchmark for refugee integration](#). It is a comparative, indicator-based assessment of the refugee integration frameworks in place in Czechia, France, Greece, Hungary, Italy, Latvia, Lithuania, the Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovenia, Spain and Sweden.
- PandaPAS. Pre and post - Arrival schemes to facilitate inclusion and prevent xenophobia and radicalization
 - "Welcome!" Collection of good practices already existing for refugees' welcoming and first inclusion, (final version June 2018). http://www.pandpasproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2018/10/Good_Practices.pdf
- Proximity Project. Policing against Racism, Xenophobia and other Forms of Intolerance.

- Sonia Pozzi, Deborah De Luca y Prof. Maurizio Ambrosini (2018). Comparative study of best practices: services, structure, strategies and methodologies in community policing against racism, xenophobia and other forms of intolerance.
http://www.mitramiss.gob.es/oberaxe/ficheros/documentos/InformePoliciaProximidad_en.pdf
- RESCUE Project
 - Best Practices Selection are based on: Social integration measures, Labour market integration measures, Access to education, Financial support, Integration into the educational institution, Social and legal assistance and Network / Alliances. <https://www.rescuerefugees.eu/best-practices-selection/>
- UNHCR: The Global Refugee Forum
 - It “provides an opportunity for States and other stakeholders to exchange and showcase good practices and experiences, both with respect to specific country or regional situations, as well as on a global level”: <https://www.unhcr.org/good-practices.html>

4 Identification of key issues for Tailored Attention and Inclusion Strategies TAISs

4.1 Previous consideration

TAIS are innovative as they define effective practices (i.e. highly scored by criteria) for a given context describing the correspondence between Vulnerability Contexts, implemented practices and criteria for their evaluation. The following step is a natural move from the Identification of (good) attention and inclusion practices.

ARU work will create the criteria (SO3) and the mapping (SO4), as tools to match vulnerable groups and their needs with suitable practices.

ARUS start working on:

- Collaborative partners' feedback and contributions for TAIS definition and guidelines:
 - Identifying priorities after main results have been presented.
 - Matching VGs-needs with suitable practices, identifying requirements for success.
 - Identifying leading ARU's members for TAISs.
 - Identifying actors' criteria to evaluate situations and practices, definitions and so on.
- Design TAIS:
 - Target VG and type of host community.
 - Application setting: context, objectives, length.
 - Requirements/accessibility issues, performance procedures.

Once RAISD stakeholders within the ARU are discussing different criteria to evaluate strategies and practices for attention and inclusion of vulnerable groups of FDP, we can move forward -although in parallel- towards the Tailored Attention and Inclusion Strategies (TAIS) design.

RAISD considers that effective and appropriate strategies of attention and inclusion to VGs of FDP need to be tailored to their specific vulnerable contexts. Experimentation will take place throughout a "Tailored Attention and Inclusion Strategies (TAISs)" pilot projects (7 projects).

It would be ideal to identify at least 3 feasible practices for each type of vulnerable group identified, and then, select the one most viable and that counts with more ARU's members support.

It is important to underline that in this planning we are looking for the sustainability of TAISs from the beginning.

Each ARU will implement the recommended practices in one pilot looking for the sustainability.

The seven pilots will provide feedback to validate the previous results in terms of whether the criteria provided a real assessment of the actors' interests, the practices could be applied in the vulnerable context, and the results obtained were those expected (SO6).

This experience will be used in the development and evaluation of the methodology and guidelines (SO5).

Key questions ARUs have to start addressing at this phase of the project are:

a) Context and levels of intervention

- I. Micro level: individual / interpersonal
- II. Meso level: institutional
- III. Macro level: policy / law. It is highly improbable that we can achieve results on the macro level during the project's life course.

Macro vs. Meso/Micro level: Macro level is the context to keep in mind all the time. Recommendations can be written aimed at the macro level. BUT: TAIS should be implemented on the meso/micro level. If there is an obstacle found on the macro level, which makes a given TAIS proposal unfeasible, it should be modified to something feasible

Meso level is for institutions and organisations, such as:

- Refugee reception facility.
- Service centre (general for all citizens or refugee-specific facility).
- Community-based organisation (migrant NGO, pro-migrant NGO, relief agency).

Types of intervention or change can be:

- Material change (improvement of material environment).
- Improved accessibility (information, opening hours, location, language).
- Procedural improvement (new or different services, methodologies).
- Changes in skills / attitude / knowledge of staff.

Micro level is for individuals, such as:

- Expert staff (service provider).
- Migrant/refugee individuals already in a vulnerability context.
- Migrant/refugee individuals at risk of becoming vulnerable.

Types of intervention or change can be:

- Awareness raising and improvement of interpersonal and intercultural skills.
- Prevention of critical situations.
- Rehabilitation restorative interventions.
- Self-help and peer support.
- Monitoring and improvement of work methodologies.

b) Criteria for effective TAIS

SMART criteria

- Specific: it should be very clear what the TAIS plans to achieve (elevator pitch / granny test).
- Measurable: the change should be defined and properly measured via indicators.
- Attainable: micro and meso level targets should be set, in a proportionate manner (time and money inputs should bring sufficient outputs).

- Relevant: It should be related to vulnerability (conceptual relevance) and to existing needs based on the interviews and ARUs (empirical relevance).
- Sustainable: It should be included the indicators that guarantee its continuity over time beyond the duration of the project.
- Time-based: A full project cycle should be planned, and the timeframe should be realistic/feasible.

Indicators

- Hierarchy: input/output – outcome/result – impact.
- Suggestion: lower level indicators should be set (input/output).
- Perspective: process-oriented – result-oriented.
- Suggestion: result-oriented indicators should be given priority.
- Evaluation: baseline, interim, final.
- Suggestion: baseline and final are a must, interim indicators only if reasonable.

c) Topics for discussion

- I. Timeline of TAIS deliverables.
- II. Agency in TAIS: Who will implement the TAIS activities? Based on what 'mandate', selection criteria, budget? What roles/functions will be assigned to ARUs, stakeholders, beneficiaries? What types of activities are eligible? (services provided, consultancy offered, etc.) Does the activity really respond to the needs detected in the vulnerable group?
- III. Framing vulnerability in TAIS: How do you conceptualize vulnerability for TAIS? Deficiency/needs of a person? Context from which a person should be rescued? Vulnerability as social deprivation? Is vulnerability a function of social status? Lived (past) or possible (future) vulnerability? Inputs from interviews would be needed – what kind of vulnerabilities are found, how can analytical categories be built – violence encountered, age, family context, etc.

4.2 Working on evaluation criteria

In parallel, **work on evaluation criteria** should be done as it is part of TAIS design. In this sense, a basic preliminary questionnaire for the ARUs includes:

Early ideas/descriptions of possible pilots

- Most importantly: Why this/these particular pilot(s)? What is the problem/vulnerability the pilots are trying to fix/alleviate?
- Who are the providers of the service/practice? Who are the end-users?
- The number and endurance of the pilots in your country.

What should be the outcome of the pilot(s)?

- What should be evaluated (e.g. change in FDPs/service providers'/stakeholders' behaviour/wellbeing/perceptions/discourses, change in external conditions)? Some other 'value' that the pilot includes?
- Thus, are you trying to e.g. promote the wellbeing, promote societal participation, increase access to services or increase the feeling of belonging to certain community/society, or something else?
- In addition to outcomes, could the pilot be evaluated in other terms such as acceptability, viability, inexpensiveness etc.?

What types of data/information could be available?

- Subjective data (perceptions of the people involved)?
- Objective data (information independent of the participating actors' perceptions)?
- Quantitative and/or qualitative data sets?
- Who will be your informants? End-users (FDPs), service providers, researchers, other stakeholders...
- What kind of methods could be used to collect the data (surveys, interviews, observations, registers, online data...)?
- How much data could be provided and in how many waves? Are you able to produce data before, during and after the pilot(s)?

Annex 1. H2020 Glossary

The European Commission facilitates a Glossary that some partners less familiar with H2020 requisites and development might find useful. Available at: <https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/support/glossary>

Annex 2. References of Scientific Journals

The Scientific Journals³⁴ of interest for the project are:

- African and Black Diaspora: An International Journal <http://www.tandfonline.com/toc/rabd20/current>
- African Diaspora: A Journal of Transnational Africa in a Global World <http://www.brill.com/african-diaspora>
- Africana: A Journal of Ideas on Africa and the African Diaspora <http://africanajournal.org/>
- Anti-Trafficking Review <http://www.antitraffickingreview.org/index.php/atrjournal/index>
- Black Diaspora Review <https://scholarworks.iu.edu/journals/index.php/bdr/about>
- Central and Eastern European Migration Review <http://www.ceemr.uw.edu.pl/>
- Citizenship Studies <http://www.tandfonline.com/toc/ccst20/current>
- Comparative Migration Studies
<http://www.springer.com/social+sciences/population+studies/journal/40878?det>
- Crossings: Journal of Migration & Culture <http://www.intellectbooks.co.uk/journals/view-journal,id=173/>
- Diaspora: A Journal of Transnational 1044-2057 <http://muse.jhu.edu/journal/321>
- Diaspora, Indigenous, and Minority Education: Studies of Migration, Integration, Equity, and Cultural Survival
<http://www.tandfonline.com/toc/hdim20/current>
- Diaspora Studies <http://www.tandfonline.com/toc/rdst20/current>
- Ethnicities <http://etn.sagepub.com/>
- Ethnicity & Health <http://www.tandfonline.com/toc/ceth20/current>
- European Journal of Migration and Law <http://www.brill.com/european-journal-migration-and-law>
- Forced Migration Review <http://www.fmreview.org/index.html>
- Georgetown Immigration Law Journal <http://www.law.georgetown.edu/academics/law-journals/gilj/index.cfm>
- Global Networks: A Journal of Transnational Affairs [http://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/journal/10.1111/\(ISSN\)1471-0374](http://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/journal/10.1111/(ISSN)1471-0374)
- Identities: Global Studies in Culture and Power <http://www.tandfonline.com/toc/gide20/current>
- Immigrants & Minorities: Historical Studies in Ethnicity, Migration and Diaspora
<http://www.tandfonline.com/toc/fimm20/current>
- Immigration and Nationality Law Review <http://www.law.uc.edu/journals/inlr>
- International Journal of Migration and Residential Mobility
<http://www.inderscience.com/jhome.php?jcode=ijmrm#moredesc>
- International Journal of Migration and Border Studies <http://www.inderscience.com/jhome.php?jcode=ijmbs>
- International Journal of Migration, Health and Social Care
<http://emeraldgroupublishing.com/products/journals/journals.htm?id=ijmhsc>
- International Journal of Refugee Law <http://ijrl.oxfordjournals.org/>
- International Migration [http://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/journal/10.1111/\(ISSN\)1468-2435](http://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/journal/10.1111/(ISSN)1468-2435)
- International Migration Review [http://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/journal/10.1111/\(ISSN\)1747-7379](http://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/journal/10.1111/(ISSN)1747-7379)

³⁴ Source: IOM (no date) Migration Journals Retrieved from https://www.iom.int/sites/default/files/our_work/ICP/MPR/Migration-Journals-EN.pdf

- Journal of Ethnic and Migration Studies <http://www.tandfonline.com/loi/cjms20>
- Journal of Ethnic and Racial Studies <http://www.tandfonline.com/toc/rers20/current>
- Journal of Human Trafficking <http://www.tandfonline.com/toc/uhmt20/current>
- Journal of Identity and Migration Studies <http://jims.e-migration.ro/Home.php>
- Journal of Immigrant and Minority Health <http://link.springer.com/journal/10903>
- Journal of Immigrant and Refugee Studies <http://www.tandfonline.com/toc/wimm20/current>
- Journal of Immigration, Asylum & Nationality Law <http://www.bloomsburyprofessional.com/uk/journal/journal-of-immigration-asylum-and-nationality-law/>
- Journal of Intercultural Studies <http://www.tandfonline.com/toc/cjis20/current>
- Journal of International Migration and Integration <http://www.springer.com/social+sciences/population+studies/journal/12134>
- Journal of Migration History <http://www.brill.com/products/journal/journal-migration-history>
- Journal of Palestinian Refugee Studies <http://www.prc.org.uk/portal/index.php/publications/jprs>
- Journal of Race, Ethnicity and Politics <https://www.cambridge.org/core/journals/journal-of-race-ethnicity-and-politics>
- Journal of Refugee Studies <http://jrs.oxfordjournals.org/>
- Journal of Trafficking and Human Exploitation <http://www.uitgeverijparis.nl/en/journals/journal/15>
- Journal of Trafficking, Organized Crime and Security <http://www.brownwalker.com/ojs/index.php/JTOCS/index>
- Journal on Migration and Human Security <http://jmhs.cmsny.org/index.php/jmhs/index>
- Mashriq and Mahjar: Journal of Middle East Migration Studies <http://lebanesestudies.ojs.chass.ncsu.edu/index.php/mashriq/index>
- Middle East Journal of Refugee Studies <http://www.prc.org.uk/portal/index.php/publications/jprs>
- Migration and Development 2163-2324 <http://www.tandfonline.com/loi/rmad20>
- Migration and Ethnic Themes /Migracijske I etničke teme <https://ojs.imin.hr/index.php/met/issue/archive>
- Migration Information Source <http://www.migrationpolicy.org/programs/migration-information-source>
- Migration Studies <https://migration.oxfordjournals.org/>
- Mobilities <http://www.tandfonline.com/toc/rmob20/current>
- Nationalism and Ethnic Politics <http://www.tandfonline.com/toc/fnep20/current>
- Nordic Journal of Migration Research <https://www.degruyter.com/view/j/njmr>
- Oxford Monitor of Forced Migration <http://oxmofm.com/>
- Population, Space and Place [http://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/journal/10.1002/\(ISSN\)1544-8452](http://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/journal/10.1002/(ISSN)1544-8452)
- Refuge: Canada's Journal on Refugees /Refuge : revue canadienne sur les réfugiés <http://refuge.journals.yorku.ca/index.php/refuge/index>
- Refugee Survey Quarterly <http://rsq.oxfordjournals.org/>
- Remittances Review <http://tplondon.com/rem/>
- Rural Migration News <https://migration.ucdavis.edu/rmn/>
- Slavery Today: A Multidisciplinary Journal of Human Trafficking Solutions <http://slaverytoday.org/journal-home/>
- Sociology of Race and Ethnicity <http://sre.sagepub.com/content/current>

- South Asian Diaspora <http://www.tandfonline.com/toc/rsad20/current>
- Studi Emigrazione: International Journal of Migration Studies <http://cser.it/scientific-journal/#>
- Studies in Ethnicity and Nationalism [http://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/journal/10.1111/\(ISSN\)1754-9469](http://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/journal/10.1111/(ISSN)1754-9469)
- The Journal of Interrupted Studies <http://jis-oxford.co.uk/index.html>
- The Journal of Migration and Refugee Issues <https://www.informit.org/product-details/615/JMRI/titles>

Annex 3. References of crosswise literature

In the following paragraphs we point out several interesting comparative/European-scope research initiatives related to RAISD's objectives (and its forthcoming tasks):

- Aguaded Ramírez, E.M., Bartolomei Torres, P., & Angelidou, A. (2018). Analysis of a project conducted on unaccompanied refugees' children (MERNAs). *NAER: Journal of New Approaches in Educational*, 7(2) (Universities in the digital age: challenges and opportunities), 116-124.
- Álvarez Jiménez, G., & Padrós Cuxart, M. (2017). How Solidarity Influences Political Actors to Manage the Refugee Crisis: The Case of Proactiva Open Arms. *RIMCIS: Revista Internacional y Multidisciplinar en Ciencias Sociales*, 6(2), 215-229.
- Bauböck, R., & Helbling, M. (2011) (eds.): *Which indicators are most useful for comparing citizenship policies?* RSCAS Working Paper 2011/54 (European University Institute, Robert Schuman Centre for Advanced Studies, EUDO Citizenship Observatory).
- Beine, M. et al., (2014). *Measuring Immigration Policies: Preliminary Evidence from IMPALA*. CESifo Working Paper Series No. 5109.
- Beine, M. et al. (2016). Comparing immigration policies: An overview from the IMPALA database. *International Migration Review*, 50 (4), 827-863.
- Bjerre, L.; Helbling, M.; Römer, F., & Zobel, M. (2016). *Technical Report: The Immigration Policies in Comparison (IMPIC) Dataset*. WZB Berlin Social Science Center. Discussion Paper. SP VI 2016–201.
- Bueno Doral, T.R., & García Castillo, N. (2016). Gender-related persecution and asylum right in international jurisprudence: advances and challenges, *Derecom*, 21.
- Busetta, A. et al., (2019). Measuring vulnerability of asylum seekers and refugees in Italy, *Journal of Ethnic and Migration Studies*, DOI: 10.1080/1369183X.2019.1610368.
- Costa, A.L. et al. (2019). Professionals' key knowledge, competences and practices to promote social inclusion of refugees. *International Journal of Inclusive Education*, DOI: 10.1080/13603116.2019.1678777
- Costello, C., & Hancox, E., (2015). The Recast Asylum Procedures Directive 2013/32/EU: Caught between the Stereotypes of the Abusive Asylum Seeker and the Vulnerable Refugee. In V. Chetail, P. De Bruycker & F. Maiani (eds) *Reforming the Common European Asylum System: The New European Refugee Law* (Martinus Nijhoff, 2015); Oxford Legal Studies Research Paper No. 33/2015. Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=2609897>
- De Coninck, D. (2019). Migrant categorizations and European public opinion: diverging attitudes towards immigrants and refugees, *Journal of Ethnic and Migration Studies*. doi: 10.1080/1369183X.2019.1694406.
- De Haas, H., Natter, K. (2015). *The determinants of migration policies. Does the political orientation of governments matter?* IMI Working Paper Series, 117.
- De Haas, H., Natter, K., & Vezzoli, S. (2014). *Compiling and coding migration policies: Insights from the DEMIG POLICY database*. IMI Working Paper Series 87. Oxford: International Migration Institute, University of Oxford.

- De Haas, H., Natter, K. and Vezzoli, S. (2015). Conceptualizing and measuring migration policy change. *Comparative Migration Studies*, 3(15).
- De Haas, H. et al, (2015). Growing restrictiveness or changing selection? The nature and evolution of migration policies. *Comparative Migration Studies*, 3(15).
- European Commission (EC) (2018) 'Guidance note: Research on refugees, asylum seekers & migrants': http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/other/hi/guide_research-refugees-migrants_en.pdf
- Freedman, J. (2016). Sexual and gender-based violence against refugee women: a hidden aspect of the refugee "crisis". *Reproductive Health Matters*, 24:47, 18-26, DOI: 10.1016/j.rhm.2016.05.003
- Gest; J; et al., (2014). Measuring and Comparing Immigration Policies Globally: Challenges and Solutions. *Global Policy*, 5(3).
- Hansen, L. (2017). *Serving Refugee Populations - The Next Financial Inclusion Frontier: Guidelines for Financial Service Providers*. Social Performance Task Force (SPTF)- United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees (UNHCR). Online at: <https://sptf.info/images/Guidelines-for-FSPs-on-serving-refugee-populations-March2017.pdf>
- Hausemer, P. et al. (2019). *MIGRARE – Impacts of refugee flows to territorial development in Europe*. Applied Research Final Report 17/09/2019. Online at: <https://www.espon.eu/refugee>
- Helbling, M. (2013). Validating Integration and Citizenship Policy Indices. *Comparative European Politics* 11(5), 555-576.
- Helbling, M. (2016). Immigration, Integration and Citizenship Policies: Indices, Concepts and Analyses. In G.P. Freeman, & and N. Mirilovic, N. (Eds.), *Handbook of Migration and Social Policy*. Edward Elgar, pp.28-41.
- Helbling, M., Bjerre, L., Römer, F., & Zobel, M. (2016). *International Organisation of Migration (IOM) Measuring well-governed migration: The 2016 Migration Governance Index*. The Economist Intelligence Unit, London.
- Helbling, M., Bjerre, L., Römer, F., Zobel, M. (2017). Measuring immigration policies: The IMPIC database. *European Political Science*, 16(1): 79-98.
- Helbling, M., Leblang, D. (2019): Controlling immigration? How regulations affect migration flows. *European Journal of Political Research*. Retrieved from <https://ejpr.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/full/10.1111/1475-6765.12279>
- Helbling, M., Kalkum, D. (2018). Migration Policy Trends in OECD Countries. *Journal of European Public Policy* 25(12), 1779-1797.
- Helbling, M., & Michalowski, I. (2017): A New African migration: trends, patterns, drivers for Migration and Citizenship Policy Research. *Comparative Political Studies* 50(1), 3-13.
- Helbling, M., & Michalowski, I. (Eds.). (2017). Immigration and Citizenship Policy Indices: Effects and Consequences. *Comparative Political Studies* 50(1).

Helbling, M., Bjerre, L., Römer, F., & Zobel, M. (2017). Measuring Immigration Policies: The IMPIC Database. *European Political Science* 16(1), 79-98.

Internal Displacement Monitoring Center. Durable solutions: principles and process. www.internal-displacement.org

Jacobsen, K., & Landau, L.B. (2003). The Dual Imperative in Refugee Research: Some Methodological and Ethical Considerations in Social Science Research on Forced Migration. *Disasters*, 27(3), 185-206.

Kabranian-Melkonian, S. (2015). Ethical Concerns with Refugee Research. *Journal of Human Behavior in the Social Environment*, 25(7) 714-722. doi: 10.1080/10911359.2015.1032634

Koos S., & Seibel, V. (2019). Solidarity with refugees across Europe. A comparative analysis of public support for helping forced migrants. *European Societies*, 21:5, 704-728. doi: 10.1080/14616696.2019.1616794.

Matthis Schick, A. et al. (2016). Challenging future, challenging past: the relationship of social integration and psychological impairment in traumatized refugees. *European Journal of Psychotraumatology*, 7:1. doi: 10.3402/ejpt.v7.28057

Nasr, L., Fisk, R.P. (2019). The global refugee crisis: how can transformative service researchers help? *The Service Industries Journal*, 39:9-10, 684-700. doi: 10.1080/02642069.2018.1445224

Römer, F. (2017). Generous to All or "Insiders Only"? Welfare State Generosity and Immigrant Welfare Rights. *Journal of European Social Policy* 27(2) 173–196.

Sarzin, Z. (2017). *Stocktaking of Global Forced Displacement Data*. Policy Research working paper 7985. Washington, DC.: World Bank. <https://openknowledge.worldbank.org/handle/10986/26183>

Schmid, S.D., & Helbling, M., (2016). *Validating the Immigration Policies in Comparison (IMPIC) Dataset*. WZB Berlin Social Science Center. Discussion Paper. SP VI 2016–202.

Sijbrandij, M. et al., (2017). Strengthening mental health care systems for Syrian refugees in Europe and the Middle East: integrating scalable psychological interventions in eight countries. *European Journal of Psychotraumatology*, 8:sup2. doi: 10.1080/20008198.2017.1388102

Steele, L.G., & Abdelaaty, L. (2019). Ethnic diversity and attitudes towards refugees. *Journal of Ethnic and Migration Studies*, 45:11, 1833-1856. doi: 10.1080/1369183X.2018.1513785

Valcárcel Silvela, A. (2018). I was a stranger and you welcomed me: The response of the Christian civil society to refugee protection in Europe. *Revista de fomento social*, 289, 91-114.

UNDG (2004) Guidance Note on Durable Solutions for Displaced Persons (refugees, internally displaced persons, and returnees) <https://www.refworld.org/pdfid/4a54bbf4d.pdf>

UNHCR (2018) Global Trends - Forced Displacement in 2017: <https://www.unhcr.org/globaltrends2017>

UNHCR. (2018.ç) Global Trends: forced displacement in 2017 (UNHCR, June 2018): <https://www.unhcr.org/globaltrends2017/>

UNHCR. Population Statistics <http://popstats.unhcr.org/en/overview>

UNHCR. Refugee situations <https://data2.unhcr.org/en/situations> &
<https://data2.unhcr.org/en/situations/mediterranean>

UNHCR - Figures at a Glance <https://www.unhcr.org/data.html>

World Bank (2017). *Forcibly Displaced: Toward a Development Approach Supporting Refugees, the Internally Displaced, and Their Hosts.* Washington, DC: World Bank.
<https://openknowledge.worldbank.org/handle/10986/25016>

Annex 4. ARU reporting template

Guide: Guidelines for the establishing of an ARU (UNIMED, August 2019).

The start-up of the ARU

This section only needs to be filled in after the start-up phase of the ARU.

1. Which problems did you encounter in the process of starting up the ARU?
2. Was there any problem in obtaining a specific space where to set up the ARU?
3. Was there any problem in the selection/assignment of the staff involved in the management of the ARU?
4. Was there any problem in connecting the ARU with other experts of your organisation?
5. How is the ARU currently organized/structured?

The functioning of the ARU

1. Since when is the ARU operational?
2. Did the ARU start involving all the foreseen members immediately?
3. Have all the foreseen activities been planned immediately?
4. Is the ARU renowned among the prospective members/stakeholders?
5. Is the ARU accepted by the prospective members/stakeholders?
6. Do the actual members/stakeholders belong to expected target group?
7. Are there other members/stakeholders?
8. Is the quintuple helix represented?

The staff of the ARU

1. How many people are dedicated to the ARU management?
2. Are they permanent or temporary staff?
3. Are they full-time or part-time?
4. How were they selected?
5. Do you have suggestions to enhance their knowledge and skills?

The TAIs pilot courses activated in the ARU

1. Has the ARU already activated pilot courses?
2. If yes, how many people have been participating?
3. If not, when the ARU planning to organise pilot courses?

4. Who are/will be the beneficiaries of such pilot courses?
5. Who will be teaching such pilot courses?
6. Which is the expected learning outcome of these pilot courses?

The dissemination/communication tools of the ARU

1. Which are the main dissemination and communication tools of the ARU?
2. Are they effective and useful?
3. Is there something missing in terms of dissemination and/or communication?
4. Is the ARU described and its activities included in the institutional website of your organisation?
5. Do you have data on number of participants at the ARU first workshop?
6. How do you promote the ARU within your stakeholders' community?

The future sustainability plans for the ARU

1. Do you think that the objectives of the ARU have been met?
2. Do you think that the objectives of the ARU are still valid?
3. Do you suggest other/additional objectives?
4. According to your opinion, if compared to today's performance, how sustainable will the ARU be in the next future?
5. Which actions could you envisage to ensure its sustainability?
6. Which arguments could you suggest to make sure that the ARU will be sustainable after the project ends?
7. Do you have specific suggestions with regard to their sustainability?

Annex 5. Informed Consent Form

PROJECT TITLE	Reshaping Attention and Inclusion Strategies for Distinctively vulnerable people among the forcibly displaced
PROJECT ACRONYM	RAISD
GRANT AGREEMENT NUMBER	822688
CALL AND TOPIC	Migration-08-2018 Addressing the challenge of forced migration
FUNDING SCHEME	Horizon 2020 - Research and Innovation Action
PROJECT DATES	1/2/2019 - 31/1/2022

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 programme under grant agreement 822688.

1. INTRODUCTION

You have been invited to take part in a research study. Before making a decision on whether you want to participate or not, please read this document carefully. We will guarantee that you understand all the provided information, so let us know if you need an interpreter. Please ask all the questions you may have, so you can be completely sure to understand all the proceedings of the study, including risks and benefits. This informed consent document may include words that you do not understand. If this is the case, please ask the contact researcher or any other member of the study to fully explain the meaning of the word or piece of information you do not accurately understand. We assure the compliance of the project proceedings with the current legislation.

2. PURPOSE OF THE PROJECT

Reshaping Attention and Inclusion Strategies for Distinctively vulnerable people among the forcibly displaced (RAISD) The project 'Reshaping Attention and Inclusion Strategies for Distinctively vulnerable people among the forcibly displaced' (RAISD) addresses the need for effective strategies for the attention and inclusion of **distinctively Vulnerable Groups** among Forcibly Displaced People. Its' **overall objective is to identify these groups, their specific challenges and needs, to be able to discover and provide Tailored Attention and Inclusion Strategies** for them. Data acquisition in the Project will consist of surveys, questionnaires, interviews and focus groups.

3. DURATION OF THE RESEARCH ACTIVITIES

Project activities will last 36 months from 02/2019 to 01/2022.

4. RISKS OR INCONVENIENCES

No risk is foreseen. We will guarantee the protection of your data and its anonymisation in all phases of this investigation. We have an ethical committee that oversees this and a specific **procedure for incidental findings**, such as references to human trafficking, human rights violations, child abuses, etc. You are only requested to be available to participate.

5. BENEFITS

To decide for each partner: Those who are involved in the research should be compensated for time and effort. Usually, this compensation is provided as cash, voucher or some gift. You will receive small cash compensation, a voucher or a gift for your dedication.

With your participation you will make a substantial contribution to **discover and provide Tailored Attention and Inclusion Strategies** for Vulnerable Groups among Forcibly Displaced People.

6. PRIVACY AND CONFIDENTIALITY

Responses you give in the questionnaires, interviews, workshops and focus groups will be recorded. Your recorded data will not include any personal identification, so it will not be possible to identify you afterwards.

Information will be processed during the phase of data analysis and will be shown in project reports. It will not be possible to identify the source of the information. The results of this investigation may be published in scientific journals or at conferences and may be used in further studies. None of the provided personal data will be given to third parties. The responsible for data custody will be Rubén Fuentes (Universidad Complutense de Madrid, Spain).

The authorisation for the use and access to this information is valid until the end of the study unless you decide to cancel it before. If you should decide to deny your consent, please contact the investigator and let her/him know of your intention of leaving the study.

Your decision to whether or not give your authorisation for the use and diffusion of the information provided by you is completely voluntary. However, if you do not provide the investigators with this authorisation now or if you cancel it in the future, you will not be able to participate in this study.

You can request to be interviewed by a female researcher if you feel more comfortable to share your experiences that way.

Please notice that your participation in the study will not contribute to facilitate your future residence in the EU or the determination of your refugee status by any national authorities.

7. CONTACT PERSONS

In case of any issue involving you in your role of participant of this research study, you are invited to inform the national project coordinator (**data to be included in each participant country**). The local representative will be (**to be filled by each partner organisation including email address**).

8. CONFIRMATION

Your participation in this study is only possible if you freely and independently sign this consent to authorise us to use the data you provide. If you do not wish to do so, please do not participate in this study.

I hereby declare:

I am 18 years or older and I am competent to provide consent;

- I have been fully informed about the aims and purposes of the Project. I understand that there is no compulsion to participate in the Project and, if I choose to participate, I may at any stage withdraw my participation;

- I have read, or had read to me, a document providing information about this research and this consent form. I have had the opportunity to ask questions and all my questions have been answered to my satisfaction, and I fully understand the description of the research that is being provided to me;
- I agree that my data (collected by surveys, questionnaires, interviews or focus groups) is used for scientific purposes and I have no objection that my data is published in scientific publications in a way that does not reveal my identity);
- I understand that, subject to the constraints above, no recordings will be replayed in any public forum or made available to any audience other than the current researchers/research team;
- I freely and voluntarily agree to be part of this research study, though without prejudice to my legal and ethical rights;
- I understand that I may refuse to answer any question and that I may withdraw at any time without penalty;
- I understand that my participation is fully anonymous and that no personal details about me will be recorded;

Information may be shared among any of the other researcher(s) and partners participating in this Project **in an anonymous form** (namely information which does not relate to an identified or identifiable natural person or to personal data. It is rendered anonymous in such a manner that the data subject is not or no longer identifiable). All information I give will be treated as confidential. The researcher(s) will ensure to preserve my anonymity.

I have received a copy of this agreement.

This consent form is made pursuant to the relevant national, European and international data protection laws and regulations and personal data treatment obligations. Specifically, this consent document complies with the following laws and regulations:

The research project meets the data protection requirements set out in the European regulations, and specifically in the treatment of data regarding its international transfer. The Spanish law incorporates from May 25, 2018 (Royal Decree-law 5/2018, of July 27, urgent measures for the adaptation of Spanish law to the European Union regulations on data protection) the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) Regulation (EU) 2016/679 (Ref. DOUE-L-2016-80807). The research is granted with the security levels established in the legal framework.

Statement of investigator's responsibility: I have explained the nature and purpose of this research study, the procedures to be undertaken and any risks that may be involved. I have offered to answer any questions and fully answered such questions. I believe that the participant understands my explanation and has freely given informed consent.

Name and surname of the researcher:.....

Place, date and signature of the researcher:.....

Signature of the interviewee:.....

Annex 6.1 Questions for stakeholders

Q.1 What events related to emigration and immigration have been important (historical perspective)?

Analysis tips: Mesolevel. Dimension Context of arrival

Q2. Who are the actual VGs of FDP in this territory? What are their characteristics?

Analysis tips: we need to identify the relevant criteria that actors use to evaluate different aspects of FDs.

Q3. What is the current situation of unaccompanied minors, children, trafficked women, and people with disabilities?

Analysis tips: Microlevel & Mesolevel. Dimension: Context of arrival

Q4. What are the difficulties experienced by them in transit?

Analysis tips: Mesolevel

Q5. What is their history in this territory/context?

Analysis tips: Mesolevel . Dimension Context of arrival

Q6. What are the characteristics of the hosting community? What is the characterisation of the general context of arrival regarding social problems (such as: inequalities (discrimination), poverty/hunger, lack of peace, lack of justice and strong institutions (e.g.: corruption, discrimination)?

Analysis tips: Mesolevel. Dimension Context of arrival

Q7. What is the role of international organisations and border agreements (European Union, United Nations, UNHCR, International Migration Organisation...) and other specific migrants' or refugees' programmes in this territory?

Analysis tips: Macrolevel. Policies.

Q8. What is the role of National Government Policies regarding migration? (related to life conditions; decent work; health; sustainable communities; quality education; gender equality; and specific migrants' or refugees' programmes)

Analysis tips: Macrolevel. Policies.

Q9. What are the regional/local specific programs for migrants/ FDP? How do you value its contribution, strengths and weaknesses? How is the inclusion of FDP in the rest of social policies?

Analysis tips: Macrolevel. Policies.

Q10. Regarding highly vulnerable people, is there any identification of good practices? or, in your opinion, are there good care practices or positive experiences regarding the policies or programs that an institution or NGO is carrying out? What does it make it "a good practice"?

And the other way around, is there any practice to avoid?

Analysis tips: Macrolevel

** To deepen the identification of good practices, a specific session (interview, workshop, etc.) is recommended on... "With what criteria should we evaluate policies and practices of attention towards Vulnerable Groups (VGs) of forcibly displaced people (FDP)?" see Objectives and Expected Results.*

Q11. What are the perceptions from society (people, political parties, government...) regarding migrants, refugees and FDP in general? Perception, stereotypes, prejudices, discrimination practices.

Analysis tips: Mesolevel . Dimension Context of arrival

Q12. What are the difficulties experienced by VGs at the processes of inclusion in host environments? What and how are their mutual interactions?

Analysis tips: Mesolevel and exolevel.

Q13. How will you describe the roles of social institutions regarding migration and forced displacement? Education system; Job market; Religious authorities; Mass media; Judicial sphere; police/ Security

Analysis tips: Mesolevel. Socio-Economic Situation at present settlement. Roles of formal social institutions (mediation institutions).

Q14. What are host communities' perceptions about them? Is there any difference among profiles or types of migrants?

Analysis tips: Macrolevel. Society-culture at present settlement. Social and sexual organisation; work organisation; systems of beliefs; gender ideologies; cultural models; lifestyles (e.g. rural/urban).

Q15. What impact migrants' presence has had and (has or is having) on the territory? What consequences are perceived?

Analysis tips: Mesolevel. Socio-Economic Situation at present settlement.

Q16. Is civil society active? Does it have a history regarding migrants' rights? Are migrant's organisations active in the territory? How are relations among them?

Analysis tips: Mesolevel. Civil Society. Existing and historical practices of participation at present settlement. Local dimension of civil participation. Types of interactions and experiences with VG.

Mesolevel. Community at the territory (at present settlement). Reception communities. Groups' context as well as organisations (social capital and support).

Annex 6.2 Interview guide for highly vulnerable groups

Previous steps

Information about age (approximately), gender and other features should be known in advance. It is part of the key features of vulnerable groups that had led to the identification of informants.

Continuous gratitude. Give value to the time, experience and time that we are going to share

Content of the *Informed Consent Form* has been provided in advanced.

Consent is given and signed.

Questions

Start with some warm-up questions to help the participant feel comfortable.

Q1. Breaking the ice Tell me a little bit about you... How old are you, where do you come from and how come did you arrive at (name of the place)?

Analysis tips: Ontological level. Origin (region? Country? [check anonymisation]). Migration history.

Q2. What did you do in your home country, how was your life then?

Analysis tips: Ontological level. Dimension: socio-demographic profile. Dimension: civil status, socioeconomic status, Racialisation or ethnicisation, Religion, Education/training, Jobs.

Q3. Tell me about the journey you have made. Who made the decision and why did you wanted to move from your country?

Analysis tips: Ontological level. Dimension: Decision-making regarding migration (autonomous/family/other); Migration history.

Mesolevel: Dimension. Context of Departure: Inequalities (discrimination); Poverty/hunger; Lack of peace; Lack of justice and strong institutions (e.g.: corruption, discrimination). Events related to emigration and immigration (within the territory of departure).

Q4. How was your journey? Where have you been, and how long did it take you to come here?

Analysis tips: Ontological level. Dimensions: Individual transit & displacement trajectory (alone or unaccompanied, family, acquaintance network, paid network, human trafficking).

Q5. How did authorities treat you through your journey?

Analysis tips: Mesolevel.

Q6. How did the communities treat you thorough the transit?

Analysis tips: Mesolevel. Community at the territory (at present settlement). Reception communities during the transit and in destination.

Q7. How are you feeling regarding your health? Has it been always like this? Have you found proper attention to your medial needs (who, when, how)?

Analysis tips: Ontological level. Dimension: socio-demographic profile. Capability/ health, Specific Inherent Needs.

Q8. Is your family here with you? How is your relationship with them?

This question can be a highly sensitive question for women or LGTB people that escaped from their families. Thus, this question should be avoided if they do not mention this aspect of their lives freely.

Analysis tips: Microlevel. Dimension: Family and context affective-emotional. Family and affective-emotional (present) context: home, partner, family, children... Specific Inherent Needs.

Q9. What is the relationship you have with people from your own community/territory of origin? (living here, and at home)

Q10. How was it during the transit?

Analysis tips: Mesolevel . Community at the territory (at present settlement). Reception communities during the transit and in destination. Groups' context as well as organisations (social capital and support).

Q11. What are you doing for living now? And how is it going for housing/working/studying or learning...? (difficulties, experiences...)

Analysis tips: Microlevel. Socioeconomic situation: status, employment. Specific Inherent Needs. Mesolevel. Socio-Economic Situation at present settlement. Education system; job market;

Analysis tips: Macrolevel. Dimensions: Society-culture at present settlement. Social and sexual organisation; work organisation; systems of beliefs; gender ideologies; cultural models; lifestyles (e.g. rural/urban). Perception of barriers or opportunities for inclusion. Macrolevel. Policies: Life conditions; Decent work; Health; Sustainable communities; Quality education; Gender equality; Specific migrants' or refugees' programs.

Q12. I don't know if religion is very important in your personal life, but are you having difficulties to express or practice your faith? Could you tell me about it?

Analysis tips: Mesolevel. Socio-Economic Situation at present settlement .Roles of formal social institutions (mediation institutions). Religious authorities.

Analysis tips: Macrolevel. Dimensions: Society-culture at present settlement. Social and sexual organisation; work organisation; systems of beliefs; gender ideologies; cultural models; lifestyles (e.g. rural/urban). Perception of barriers or opportunities for inclusion.

Q13. I would like to know a little bit more about the experiences you are having with local population here (better use local or national demonym). How are your relationships with them? Why? What do you feel about their attitudes towards displaced people?

Analysis tips: Mesolevel . Community at the territory (at present settlement). Reception communities during the transit and in destination. Types of interactions and VG experiences with them.

Analysis tips: Macrolevel. Dimensions: Society-culture at present settlement. Social and sexual organisation; work organisation; systems of beliefs; gender ideologies; cultural models; lifestyles (e.g. rural/urban). Perception of barriers or opportunities for inclusion.

Q14. Does anybody or any organisation help you to feel part of this new community? How were your experiences in this regard?

Analysis tips: Mesolevel. Community at the territory (at present settlement). Reception communities during the transit and in destination. Types of interactions and VGs experiences with them.

Analysis tips: Macrolevel. Dimensions: Society-culture at present settlement. Social and sexual organisation; work organisation; systems of beliefs; gender ideologies; cultural models; lifestyles (e.g. rural/urban). Perception of barriers or opportunities for inclusion.

Q15. Are you taking part of any organisation? How is your experience? How has it been?

Analysis tips: Mesolevel. Dimension: Civil Society. Local dimension of civil participation. Types of interactions and VG experiences with them

Analysis tips: Mesolevel. Community at the territory (at present settlement). Reception communities during the transit and in destination. Groups' context as well as organisations (social capital and support). Types of interactions and VG experiences with them.

Q16. And what about authorities? What experiences you had with Police, judges... How do you feel about their attitudes towards displaced people? Analysis tips: Macrolevel. Perception of barriers or opportunities for inclusion.

Q17. Journalists, newspapers, television... sometimes talk about the situation of people who are living moments similar to yours. What do you think about what they tell us?

Analysis tips: Macrolevel.

Q18. Have you ever taken part in a specific migrants' or refugees' programme? How was it/how it is? How is your experience? Why? What would you change of them?

Analysis tips: Macrolevel. Dimension: Policies: Life conditions; Decent work; Health; Sustainable communities; Quality education; Gender equality;

Q19. From your experience, and in your opinion, are there good care practices or positive experiences regarding the policies or programs that an institution or NGO is carrying out? And the other way around, is there any practice to avoid?

Analysis tips: Macrolevel

Q20. If this issue has not already arisen ... It is very common to have difficulties in life if people have an affective and sexual orientation other than heterosexual, or if they feel that their identity is different from their sex at birth. Has this been your case? How has your experience been in this regard? If the interviewee has not mentioned it before, we should ask this question in a more indirect way, for example: Have you ever have any kind of problem because of your partner? Do you have problems to find a partner?

Analysis tips: Ontological level. Dimension: socio-demographic profile. Capability/ health, Specific Inherent Needs.

Q.21 In your experience, from what you have lived, what is the current situation of unaccompanied minors, children, trafficked women, and people with disabilities?

Analysis tips: Microlevel & Mesolevel. Dimension: Context of arrival

Q22. In your opinion, comparing your experience with that of other people, do you think that you belong to a particularly vulnerable group?

(We will analyse the data to reach this conclusion; it is only to know their perceptions)? Or, to avoid stigmatisation: Do you think that you have had more difficulties than other people that have faced a similar situation?

Q23. What are your personal plans right now? And for the future?

We have finished Q24. Would you like to tell me something else?

End of interview

Gratitude: thank the time. Tell her/him how important it has been to know his/her experience.

Explain her/him that the results will be available in one or two years.

Provide information on how to access the results.

Deliver compensation.

Annex 6.3. Ethical self-evaluation

Ethical self-evaluation that guarantees that our research is relevant to the communities involved and has objectives that are not harmful or prejudicial to participants.

1. Each partner will focus on data collection working with a recognised NGO or related institution that will facilitate the specific aspects that are necessary to protect vulnerable groups. Detail the measures needed to implement in place to minimise the risk of stigmatisation. In case of doubt or more information you should contact the UCM and coordinate possible measures.
2. The direct data collection will be done by researchers with a background in refugee and asylum studies.
3. Researchers will provide an informed consent that must be signed by the members of the involved groups. The purpose is to ensure that participants fully understand the implications of being involved in the research. Participation in surveys and at the events in the project is voluntary and the participants will not be subject to any psychological, social, economic or other form of risk.
4. Researchers will guarantee the anonymity of the interviewed people throughout the process. As our team pointed out in previous research [Hänninen et al., 2013], interviews conducted by mass media sometimes reveal personal data of refugees that may pose a real danger to their lives. So, the project will take any potential measure to guarantee that anonymity, which is of paramount importance to people fearing persecution in their home country or capture by host country law enforcement agencies. Among these measures are:
 - a. A confidentiality clause in the document for researchers will be included. This intend to avoid that collaborating with the research (for instance signing consent forms), may jeopardise the FDP anonymity.
 - b. The project will only gather data essential for the specific research aims. Names, addresses, specific locations, exact dates will not be collected, nor any other specific aspect that could facilitate personal identification.
2. The researchers of each unit will ensure that there are no misunderstandings because of the language used, with the assistance of a translator when necessary.
3. Researchers will conduct the interviews to each person alone, without the supervision of other members of her/his group. This is the most effective way to safeguard their privacy, based on the experience the team had in previous projects.
4. In the case of women, the interviews will be conducted by a female researcher.
5. The study will not create unjustified expectations in participants about future residence in the EU or the determination of their asylum status.
6. Researchers will provide a small compensation to participants in the research.

The project is committed to ensure that the general benefits of its activities will warrant the involvement and efforts of their participant individuals, limiting any disturbance to them, especially in terms of protecting the identity and integrity of VGs. The project will be based on deliberative co-creation of activities and representatives of all interested stakeholders will be involved in these field activities.

The project will enable mechanisms to avoid any intentional or unintentional use of data that can bring any harm to any participant or being misused in other contexts. All partners performing research will act according to national and European legislation, and in line with national data protection provisions and the European data protection rules. They will be required to follow agreed rules for the recruitment of participants, the implementation of activities, recording, analysis and storage of data collected in the project.

The project will set up Privacy by Design rules to guarantee that all research activities address security, ethics and individuals' liberties. Any survey, interview or workshop participation will be on a voluntary basis with enough information to all parties. The information on the rights of interviewees and participants to workshops will be given verbally before the research activity starts. Agreement will be reached with organisations that provide information through documents or interviews, on the disclosure of that information and the protection of confidentiality.

All data will be stored anonymously on secure servers that has restricted, password protected access and data encryption. An identification number will be assigned to each participant. The storage and transferring of across borders, and from institution to institution, will adhere to national, institutional and EU policies, such as the FAIR Data Management guidelines, concerning safe storage and transfer of data. The use of data for analyses will not breach confidentiality.

EU researchers will not be sent to a third country, as fieldwork will be conducted by local researchers.

If ethical issues arise unexpectedly during the research process, we would contact the Commission/Agency immediately to receive appropriate help and guidance.

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The information and views set out in this report are those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect the official opinion of the European Union. Neither the European Union institutions and bodies nor any person acting on their behalf may be held responsible for the use which may be made of the information contained therein.